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Investigation on Hot water production and Steam Generation Heat Pump for Energy Efficiency in Meat Processing

Master's thesis in Sustainable Energy

Supervisor: Armin Hafner

Co-supervisor: Shuai Ren

July 2024

Norwegian University of
Science and Technology

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Acknowledgements

This report has been prepared by Rafi Ahmed as part of the requirements for a Master's thesis in Sustainable Energy Systems. This work contributes to the European ENOUGH program, aimed at reducing greenhouse gas emissions within the food industry. The thesis focuses on sustainable production methods for hot water and steam in the meat processing industry using heat pump systems. This involves modeling system configurations to maximize waste heat utilization and conducting experiments at NTNU's EPT test rig facility to optimize conditions for high-pressure hot water and steam production using a hybrid ammonia-water absorption compression heat pump system.

First and foremost, I would like to express my utmost gratitude to Almighty Allah for granting me the wonderful opportunity to pursue a Master's degree at a world-class institution like NTNU, gain new knowledge in sustainable energy systems, and appreciate the beautiful landscapes of Norway.

I am immensely grateful to my supervisor, *Professor Armin Hafner*, for transforming my rough ideas into a concrete structure and providing invaluable inspiration and feedback on my project. I am also deeply thankful to my co-supervisor, *Shuai Ren*, whose exceptional guidance and profound insights significantly shaped this project. Their enthusiastic support, unwavering patience, and motivating presence were pivotal in navigating the challenges of this research. I also owe a great deal of gratitude to *Khalid Hamid* for his invaluable theoretical and practical insights. His expertise significantly enriched our laboratory experiments, sparking innovative ideas and observations that were critical to the advancement of this project.

Words cannot adequately express my deep appreciation for my beloved and beautiful wife *Saoda*. The sacrifices she made, the hardships she endured, and the countless moments we missed during these two years of education are beyond measure. I apologize for the times I could not be present, focused instead on meeting deadlines. Your unwavering support, understanding, and love have been the bedrock of my strength.

Finally, I must express my profound gratitude to my parents and parents-in-law, who are 9,000 kilometers away, for their prayers and encouragement. A special thanks to *Munna*, *Minhaj* for helping me come to Norway for higher studies. I am also thankful to my friends in Norway—*Two Rakibs*, *two Kamruls*, *Tonu*, and *Nitu*—whose presence made me feel less homesick and provided invaluable support throughout this journey.

Thank you all for your contributions and support, which have been instrumental in completing this thesis.

Abstract

The increasing need for energy efficiency and the reduction of greenhouse gas emissions in the food industry, particularly in meat processing, highlights the significance of advanced heat pump technologies. This thesis addresses these critical issues by investigating the production of hot water and steam using a hybrid ammonia-water absorption compression heat pump (ACHP) system configured in a cascaded high-temperature heat pump (HTHP) setup, utilizing natural working fluids. This research is part of the European ENOUGH program, which aims to develop sustainable energy solutions for the food industry.

The study employed both modeling and experimental methods to optimize the ACHP system for high-pressure hot water and steam production. The cascade configuration was modeled in Dymola, where several simulations were carried out for two alternative bottom cycles, NH_3 and CO_2 , and the top cycle ACHP, to investigate the performance and potential of the cascaded system. The working domain of the HTHP was investigated based on technical and economic constraints. The ACHP model was further validated with experimental values obtained at NTNU's EPT test rig facility. The cascade system was evaluated for its ability to upgrade waste heat from seawater at 15°C from the condenser outlet of the ammonia refrigeration system to superheated steam at 193°C and 2 bar by incorporating a flash tank and a mechanical vapor compressor at the sink outlet of the ACHP.

The results demonstrated that the cascaded HTHP configurations, particularly the CO_2 -ACHP and NH_3 -ACHP cycles, achieved significant temperature lifts and high coefficients of performance (COP). The NH_3 -ACHP configuration achieved a COP of 4.06, while the CO_2 -ACHP configuration achieved a COP of 3.75. These findings highlight the system's efficiency in producing high-temperature steam and hot water, presenting a viable alternative to traditional fossil fuel-based boilers.

The implementation of ACHP systems in meat processing facilities offers substantial energy efficiency gains and environmental benefits. The study's outcomes support the potential of ACHP technology to significantly reduce greenhouse gas emissions and enhance sustainability in the food industry.

Sammendrag

Det økende behovet for energieffektivitet og reduksjon av klimagassutslipp i matindustrien, særlig i kjøttforedling, fremhever betydningen av avanserte varmepumpeteknologier. Denne avhandlingen tar for seg disse kritiske problemene ved å undersøke produksjon av varmtvann og damp ved bruk av et hybrid ammoniakk-vann absorpsjon kompresjon varmepumpesystem (ACHP) konfigurert i en kaskadert høytemperatur varmepumpe (HTHP) oppsett, som benytter naturlige arbeidsvæsker. Denne forskningen er en del av det europeiske ENOUGH-programmet, som har som mål å utvikle bærekraftige energiløsninger for matindustrien.

Studien benyttet både modellering og eksperimentelle metoder for å optimalisere ACHP-systemet for høytrykk varmtvann og dampproduksjon. Kaskadekonfigurasjonen ble modellert i Dymola, hvor flere simuleringer ble utført for to alternative bunnsykluser, NH₃ og CO₂, og toppsyklusen ACHP, for å undersøke ytelsen og potensialet til kaskadesystemet. Arbeidsområdet til HTHP ble undersøkt basert på tekniske og økonomiske begrensninger. ACHP-modellen ble videre validert med eksperimentelle verdier oppnådd ved NTNU's EPT testrigganlegg. Kaskadesystemet ble evaluert for dets evne til å oppgradere spillvarme fra sjøvann ved 15°C fra kondensatorutløpet til ammoniakk-kjølesystemet til overhetet damp ved 193°C og 2 bar ved å inkorporere en flash-tank og en mekanisk dampkompressor ved utløpet til ACHP.

Resultatene viste at de kaskaderte HTHP-konfigurasjonene, særlig CO₂-ACHP og NH₃-ACHP syklusene, oppnådde betydelige temperaturøkninger og høye ytelseskoeffisienter (COP). NH₃-ACHP-konfigurasjonen oppnådde en COP på 4,06, mens CO₂-ACHP-konfigurasjonen oppnådde en COP på 3,75. Disse funnene fremhever systemets effektivitet i å produsere høytemperaturdamp og varmtvann, og presenterer et levedyktig alternativ til tradisjonelle fossile brennstoffbaserte kjeler.

Implementeringen av ACHP-systemer i kjøttforedlingsanlegg gir betydelige gevinster i energieffektivitet og miljøfordeler. Studiens resultater støtter potensialet til ACHP-teknologi til å redusere klimagassutslipp betydelig og forbedre bærekraften i matindustrien.

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Nomenclature

Symbols

α	Heat transfer coefficient [W/m ² ·K]
k	Thermal Conductivity [W/m-K]
U	Overall heat transfer coefficient [W/m ² ·K]
ΔT	Temperature difference [K]
\dot{m}_R	Refrigerant mass-flow [kg/s]
\dot{Q}_C	Condenser heat capacity [kW]
\dot{Q}_E	Evaporator heat capacity [kW]
\dot{W}_C	Shaft Work of Compressor [kW]
η_{Is}	Isentropic Compressor Efficiency []
λ	Volumetric Compressor Efficiency []
π	Pressure ratio [-]
ρ	Mass density [kg/m ³]
A	Area [m ²]
C_P	Heat capacity [kJ/kgK]
e	Electricity cost [Euro/kWh]
h	Enthalpy [kJ/kgK]
n	Compressor speed [rpm]
n	Economic lifetime [year]
p_C	Condensation pressure [bar]
p_E	Evaporation pressure [bar]
p_{im}	Intermediate pressure [bar]

r	Interest rate [-]
T_C	Condensation Temperature [°C]
T_E	Evaporation Temperature [°C]
V_{dis}	Compressor Displacement [m ³ /h]
X	Ammonia mass fraction []
TCI	Total Capital Investment

Abbreviations

<i>ACHP</i>	Absorption Compression Heat Pump
<i>COP</i>	Coefficient of performance
<i>CR</i>	Circulation Ratio
<i>GC</i>	Gas Cooler
<i>HC</i>	Hydrocarbon
<i>HTHP</i>	High Temperature Heat Pump
<i>IHEX</i>	Internal Heat Exchanger
<i>LMTD</i>	Logarithmic Mean Temperature Difference
<i>PHEX</i>	Plate Heat Exchanger
<i>SGHP</i>	Steam Generation Heat Pump
<i>SWHP</i>	Seawater heat pump technology
HEX	Heat Exchanger
LT	Low Temperature
MT	Medium Temperature
PEC	Purchase equipment costs

1 Introduction

The work presented in this Master's thesis builds upon my specialization project conducted during the Autumn semester of 2023 [3]. While some sections of the technical background, theory, and methodology from the project report have been utilized, this thesis significantly expands upon and extends the previous research. Note that the specialization project report is unpublished.

1.1 Research Significance

Climate change is an increasingly critical threat impacting the occurrence of natural disasters worldwide. In response, the European Commission has committed to reducing greenhouse gas emissions by 80-90% by 2050 to maintain global temperature increases below 2°C, as stipulated by the Paris Agreement. This agreement also mandates emission-free new industrial facilities by 2035 [25] [81]. The EU has adopted dual strategies focusing on enhancing energy efficiency and decarbonizing the energy supply [21].

In Norway, about one-third of the energy demand originates from the industrial sector, largely due to process heat. This demand accounts for 66% and 80% in Germany and the Netherlands, respectively [31]. A substantial amount of industrial energy is released at low temperatures, rendering 60% of this heat of minimal thermal and economic value [14]. A study in the UK identified that most industrial waste heat temperatures fall between 100-200°C, with limited potential below 100°C, especially in the food and beverage industry [20]. Heat pumps have been identified as viable alternatives for supplying process heat up to 250°C [16], and it is estimated that high-temperature heat pumps could utilize approximately 75 TWh of excess heat in Europe, particularly within the paper and food industries [31].

Conventionally, industries have met their heating and cooling demands through separate systems—refrigeration and traditional boilers. While steam boilers are commonly used for their rapid heating capability and latent heat content, heat pumps offer a thermodynamic advantage by using low-temperature waste heat and renewable energy sources, thus bypassing the need for cooling towers [41].

The current limitations of heat pump systems include the maximum achievable supply temperature and pressure; they typically produce low-pressure steam, with high-pressure steam generation posing efficiency challenges [18]. However, ongoing research is exploring higher pressure and temperature steam generation using natural and synthetic fluids with low global

warming potential, through mechanical vapor compression or absorption, which has seen significant technical advancements recently [95].

The Absorption-Compression Heat Pump (ACHP) system, operating with a zeotropic ammonia-water mixture and based on the "Osenbrück cycle," offers a promising solution for achieving high sink temperatures, such as 140°C, due to its capability to operate at gliding temperatures [4]. Similarly, steam generation heat pumps (SGHPs) utilizing hydrocarbons such as R600, R600a, and R601a are also advancing, employing cascade cycles or mechanical vapor recompression to meet high-pressure steam demands in industrial applications [95].

Carbon dioxide (CO₂), a natural working fluid, becomes supercritical at 31.1°C and 73.7 bar. It has gained attention in recent decades for hot water production in domestic and industrial settings. The integration of CO₂ heat pumps for hot water production has shown significant promise due to their ability to efficiently transfer heat. A CO₂ heat pump is advantageous for a large temperature range heat rejection, resulting in a relatively low CO₂ outlet temperature from the gas cooler with a high coefficient of performance [72].

Ammonia (NH₃) in heat pumps for water heating in industrial settings is another solution for hot water production, though it has not gained much attention because of its toxicity, flammability, and constraints on achieving higher condensation temperatures. However, with the advanced development of twin screw compressors, ammonia's excellent efficiency and reliability can be utilized in two-stage ammonia heat pumps for hot water production, achieving higher supply temperatures above 60°C. Additionally, ammonia can be included in cascade systems to upgrade waste heat from refrigeration systems [91].

In the context of the food and beverage industry, particularly meat processing, integrating heat pumps for hot water and steam generation could be crucial in meeting the EU's greenhouse gas reduction targets and improving energy efficiency. This necessitates further research into the thermal energy demand spectrum, the potential for waste heat utilization (both low and high temperature), and the integration of heat pumps within the industrial process heat demands, alongside monitoring the continuing advancements in heat pump technologies.

1.2 Project ENOUGH

The ENOUGH project is a European initiative aimed at reducing greenhouse gas emissions in the food industry, which globally accounts for 20 to almost 40% of total emissions. With around 60% of food requiring refrigeration at some point and 70% of emissions linked to perishable foods, the primary sources of these emissions are energy use and leakage of high GWP refrigerants within the food chain [29].

To address this, the project will develop technical, financial, and political tools and solutions to support the EU's Farm to Fork sustainable strategy. The objectives are:

- Identify how to achieve climate neutrality for food businesses.
- Improve integrated sustainability and meet societal goals.
- Raise awareness among policymakers, businesses, investors, entrepreneurs, institutions, stakeholders, and citizens about innovative systemic solutions and their potential for widespread adoption across the EU.

The ultimate aim is to reduce greenhouse gas emissions by 2030 and achieve carbon neutrality in the food industry by 2050.

Figure 1.1: ENOUGH Project Logo

1.3 Problem Description

Thematic and modified description for the thesis based on the Master's thesis agreement

Food systems are globally responsible for approximately 21-37% of total greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions. Meat processing, in particular, requires substantial energy resources, contributing significantly to these emissions. Enhancing energy efficiency and decarbonizing the energy sector within meat processing is crucial to meet the EU framework for GHG reduction. The meat sector has a potential source of waste heat, and upgrading this waste heat through multistage heat pumps can significantly contribute to sustainable energy consumption in this sector.

Rema 1000, the owner of Norsk Kylling, operates a 35,000 m² slaughterhouse and meat processing plant in Orkanger, Orkland municipality, where 55,000-65,000 chickens are processed daily [47]. The energy systems in such processing plants are complex, involving cooling, freezing, heating, washing, drying, and HVAC equipment. In addition to meeting the dynamic cold energy demand, the processing plant has the potential to upgrade waste heat from refrigeration system condensers. This waste heat can be transformed into high-temperature water and steam using cascaded cycles of CO₂-Absorption Compression Heat Pump (ACHP) or NH₃-ACHP heat pump cycles.

The Absorption Compression Heat Pump (ACHP) is a promising steam generation technology that utilizes an ammonia-water working fluid. This technology can combine both cooling and heating processes, achieving high heat sink temperatures up to 140°C, making it a suitable replacement for fossil fuel boilers.

CO₂ and NH₃ heat pumps can be utilized to upgrade the waste heat from refrigeration condensers as a heat source in the ACHP system for different supply temperatures, such as 70, 75, 80, 85, and 90°C. This master's thesis will focus on developing simplified process configurations for cascaded systems and creating dynamic models of all configurations using the object-oriented modeling language, Modelica. The thesis will further perform simulations for varying load configurations, source, and sink conditions, and present a technical and economic evaluation of the proposed cascaded models for decision-making. The results will be analyzed, followed by a discussion, summary, and suggestions for further work. The findings aim to contribute to a more sustainable and energy-efficient meat processing industry, aligning with broader environmental goals.

1.3.1 Task Description

The following tasks are considered in this thesis work:

1. Conduct a literature review on meat processing systems and their energy requirements, heat pump cycles, components of the ACHP cycle, and natural working fluid-based steam generation heat pumps.
2. Perform an experimental investigation of the ACHP cycle on the “Osenbrück 4.0 Heat Pump” at NTNU EPT lab.
3. Develop a numerical model of the ACHP cycle and evaluate the cycle performance in terms of thermodynamic advantage and economic evaluation.
4. Conduct a comprehensive case study of the ACHP model by examining its application within a local chicken factory.
5. Process and analyze the modeling and experimental results.
6. Write a master’s thesis report, including a discussion, summary, and further work chapter.

1.4 Overview

As previously stated, this master’s thesis is a continuation of the specialization project from the Autumn semester of 2023. It serves as a foundation for the subsequent master thesis, further expanding on the initial work. The project work and its continuation into the master thesis are discussed below.

1.4.1 Project Work

The main focus of the project work was to develop an ACHP dynamic model in Dymola with the injection of a lean solution to control discharge temperature and achieve a sink outlet temperature above 120°C. This included comparing different cycle configurations, analyzing the impact of changing input parameters on the lean and rich solution properties of the ammonia-water hybrid system, evaluating the overall performance of the system, and conducting an economic evaluation to determine the feasibility of the ACHP heat pump over a conventional steam boiler. The sub-tasks included:

- Conducting a literature review of thermal demand in the meat processing industry.
- Investigating hot water and steam generation technologies.

- Reviewing technological advancements in steam generation heat pumps based on natural working fluids.
- Studying the theory behind ammonia-water absorption compression heat pumps.

1.4.2 Master's Thesis Work

The primary objective of this study is to establish numerical modeling of two cascaded systems: CO₂ Absorption Compression Heat Pump (ACHP) and NH₃-ACHP heat pump cycles. These models aim to upgrade condensation waste heat from 15°C to 120°C and beyond, producing hot water and steam. Additionally, the study aims to develop a conceptual steam generation model by introducing flash tank steam separation from high-pressure hot water in lower pressure expansion, upgrading the steam to higher pressure and temperature.

An experimental investigation of the ACHP test rig and an evaluation of its performance in comparison with the developed model in a simulation environment was conducted. The experimental work is carried out during the fall and spring semesters in the basement of the Varmeteknisk lab. The cascade systems were designed in AutoCAD to represent the conceptual P&ID of each heat pump cycle. Extensive time was spent in the calculation of convective heat transfer coefficients in the heat exchangers, except for the absorber and desorber of the ACHP system.

Three heat pump cycles were modeled in Dymola, and the flash tank concept was further investigated by designing a simple flash tank unit in the same software. Finally, a techno-economic comparative study of the proposed cycle configurations of the two cascaded systems for steam generation and hot water production was carried out. Sensitivity analysis was performed for the presented configurations of the cascades.

1.5 Thesis Structure

This report is structured into ten parts, as follows:

Chapter 2: Provides an overview of the meat processing sector, energy use in meat processing, opportunities for waste heat upgrading, and a conceptual mapping of energy recovery potential in processes, followed by a literature review of hot water and steam thermal properties in various meat processes.

Chapter 3: Covers the background concerning high-temperature heat pumps, the theory of absorption compression heat pumps including zeotropic mixtures, cycle configurations in high-temperature heat pumps, and seawater heat exchanger material selection, followed by a literature review on high-temperature heat pumps.

Chapter 4: Includes an overview of the energy central in a chicken meat processing factory, the previous work performed on it, and the scope of expanding the energy central configuration.

Chapter 5: Addresses the methodology of the numerical investigation conducted in Dymola, presents the NTNU test rig of ACHP, the reasoning behind selecting cycle configurations of the cascade system.

Chapter 6: Discusses the sequence and method followed in developing the components of each model, the controller specification and working principle, background on economic evaluation, and the overall heat transfer coefficient.

Chapter 7: Presents the results obtained from the simulation and the experimental investigation.

Chapter 8: Offers a discussion on the results, sources of errors, comparison to results found in the literature, and limitations.

Chapter 9: Concludes the report by presenting the main findings from the study.

Chapter 10: Suggests possibilities for further work to improve the investigated system both theoretically and experimentally.

2 Meat Processing Overview

This chapter addresses several key aspects of hot water and steam requirements in meat processing. It includes a comprehensive literature review, an overview of the conceptual thermal demand in meat processing plants, and explores opportunities for waste heat upgrading.

2.1 Hot Water and Steam Requirements in Meat Processing

Meat processing is generally divided into two main categories: primary and secondary processing (Figure 2.1). The meat industry primarily involves the slaughtering of cattle, sheep, pigs, and poultry such as chickens, turkeys, and ducks. It encompasses the production, storage, and packaging of these meats and poultry products. Additionally, the industry manufactures value-added products like bacon and ham and processes other meats and animal by-products [9].

Figure 2.1: Meat processing method, categories and corresponding meat products.

Meat Processing (MP) plants require substantial amounts of energy resources for their operations. As the European Union strides towards its ambitious goal for sustainable energy use, MP plants find themselves at a critical intersection. The need to adopt sustainable energy practices is not only a compliance requirement but also an objective of the EU's environmental

and economic set plan.

In 2020, the total energy consumption across all industrial sectors in Norway totaled 81,376 GWh [68]. The manufacture of food products, beverages, and tobacco was identified as the fourth-largest energy consumer within this total amount, accounting for 6% of the total energy usage. A closer examination, as illustrated in Figure 2.2, shows that within this sector, the meat processing industries—specifically the processing and preserving of meat, processing and preserving of poultry meat, and production of meat and poultry meat products—had significant shares in energy consumption corresponding to 17%, 1%, and 13% respectively. This places the meat processing sub-sector as the second-largest consumer of energy within the food manufacturing industry in Norway.

Figure 2.2: Energy consumption in the Norwegian meat processing sector.

In the meat processing and slaughter industry, energy consumption is driven by the need for both electrical and thermal energy for various operations. Electricity primarily powers refrigeration, freezing, and ventilation, making up 45% to 55% of total electricity use during workdays, particularly in cooling production and distribution. This process is the most energy-intensive in the industry [8]. Additionally, thermal energy, often sourced from fossil fuels like natural gas or diesel, is essential for operating steam boilers that produce process steam and provide warm, hot, and tap water, as well as comfort heating [32].

From heating water for scalding and cleaning to operating equipment, slaughtering livestock, and processing meat requires varied energy segments [9]. MP plant energy use can be categorized into two segments: the energy required for refrigeration and cooling demand within the facility, and

the energy required for heating, such as for tap water, building heating, and steam generation [32].

Process	Fluid Medium	Description
Animal Pre-Washing	Water or Steam	Uses water or steam at 75-80°C under atmospheric pressure to remove microbial contamination post-exsanguination. [79]
Dehairing	Water and Alkali	Involves hot water and alkali up to 66°C for scalding post-bleeding. [79]
Carcass Decontamination	Water	Applies hot water or chemical solutions between 66-87.8°C for microbial quality enhancement. [79]
	Steam	Dispenses steam or hot water at 104-110°C, 2.07-3.45 bar pressure, followed by vacuum heat sanitization. [79]
Final Carcass Washing	Water	Water-washing at 10-56°C with pressures of 3.43 to 4.13 bar, duration varies. [79]
Thermal Decontamination	Water	Hot water at 74-97°C used for microbial reduction and removal. [79]
	Steam	Steam at 99-101°C with atmospheric pressure for surface decontamination. [63]
	Steam	Uses steam at 115-130°C, 1.03 bar/atmospheric pressure. [55]
Drying	Steam	For canning, steam is used at 149°C and pre-sterilization at 232°C with respective pressures. [55]
	Steam	Employs steam at 130-160°C, 2.7-6.83 bar pressure for effective drying. [71]
Sausage Production	Steam	Hot-smoking at +65 to +70°C, part of the heat treatment for color and flavor. [35]
	Water	Cooking in hot water or steam at +74 to +80°C until core temperature reaches +72°C. [35]

Table 2.1: Summary of steam and hot water properties in various meat processing.

The thermal energy requirements in meat processing are extensive and varied. In animal pre-washing, thermal energy from water or steam at 75-80°C under atmospheric pressure is essential for removing microbial contamination post-exsanguination. Similarly, the dehairing process employs hot water and alkali up to 66°C to facilitate scalding and microbial quality improvement.

Carcass decontamination relies on thermal energy applied via hot water or chemical solutions between 66-87.8°C, and alternatively, steam at 104-110°C with pressures of 2.07-3.45 bar, followed by vacuum heat sanitization, to significantly reduce microbial load. Final carcass washing utilizes water at 10-56°C with pressures ranging from 3.43 to 4.13 bar, ensuring thorough removal of contaminants.

Thermal decontamination processes are particularly noteworthy, using hot water at 74-97°C and steam at varying conditions: 99-101°C at atmospheric pressure, 115-130°C at 1.03 bar, and even 149°C for canning, with pre-sterilization at 232°C. Drying processes further emphasize the use of thermal energy, employing steam at 130-160°C with pressures of 2.7-6.83 bar for effective

drying.

In sausage production, thermal energy plays a crucial role with hot-smoking using steam at 65-70°C to enhance color and flavor, and cooking in hot water or steam at 74-80°C until the core temperature reaches 72°C to ensure thorough cooking.

A summary of the temperature and pressure information of hot thermal energy required in meat processing, gathered from various literature reviews, is presented in Table 2.1.

2.2 Excess Heat Potential

Excess or waste heat is generated wherever goods are produced or processed and machines are operated. This heat, not needed for the process itself, has a high exergy content which can be utilized to enhance energy utilization through various technologies designed for excess heat use [20].

Temperature Range	Usage
>140°C	Power recovery with a steam turbine, ORC system/Stirling engine, or direct use for district heating. Includes combustible gas.
60-140°C	Power recovery with an ORC system or Stirling engine, and direct use for district heating.
40-60°C	Direct use for low-temperature district heating, or as a heat source for a heat pump with a good heat factor.
25-40°C	Direct use for fish farming and geothermal heating, or as a heat source for a heat pump.

Table 2.2: *Applicability of Heat Sources at Various Temperature Ranges by Utnyttelse av spillvarme fra norks industri – en potensialstudie.* [82]

In industrial processing, excess heat is termed lost heat that escapes from equipment like compressors and steam generators, as well as from pipes, walls, and heat exchangers. A great portion of this heat can be recovered and utilized for various applications to increase process efficiency. This excess heat accounts for 10 to 50% of the total thermal energy demand in industry across different countries, which can be a valuable energy resource if managed well [93].

In Norway, within the food industry, steam, water, and exhaust contribute 18%, 31%, and 51% respectively to waste heat [82]. Most food companies use both heating and cooling processes, which have a potential for internal heat exchange, possibly with a heat pump. Almost 30% of energy savings can come from using waste heat internally, particularly in industrial and auxiliary systems. Table 2.2 highlights the potential for energy savings by harnessing excess heat in these industries.

Figure 2.3 illustrates how primary energy flows in utility and processes in a typical meat processing plant. Energy use in this meat processing plant can be divided into two main categories: refrigeration systems to meet sub-ambient temperature needs and steam for above ambient temperature requirements, such as warming utility water and direct steam injection in required processes.

Steam is typically generated by burning coal, combusting natural gas, or through electricity. The hot thermal energy applications include smoking, grilling, cooking, scalding, sterilization, pasteurization, tap water heating, cleaning, and comfort heating. Steam is used in smoking, grilling, cooking, and hot water heating at 100°C, 120-180°C, 100°C, and 70°C, respectively. The hot water produced by steam is later supplied to other subprocesses of the meat plant.

The condensate from direct steam injection processes is a potential source of waste heat upgrading, as shown in the figure, and can be categorized as high-quality process wastewater. Gray water from domestic use and other wastewater from direct process use can be categorized as low quality and medium quality. Refrigeration units, condenser, desuperheater, piston compressor cooling, oil cooling of the compressor, and air compressor cooling are also potential heat sources that can be upgraded by heat pump technologies in the form of hot water or low-pressure steam.

Figure 2.3: Overview of Meat Processing Heat Recovery

3 Theory and Literature Review

3.1 Carnot Cycle

A Carnot cycle represents an idealized thermodynamic cycle, featuring four distinct stages: isothermal heat absorption, isentropic compression, isothermal heat release, and isentropic expansion, functioning with theoretically unlimited heat exchanger surface areas. This cycle is entirely reversible, facilitating the transfer of heat from a warmer to a cooler reservoir while consuming work. An example of this is the reverse Carnot cycle used in heat pumps, which extract heat from a colder source and deposit it into a warmer one through compression.

Figure 3.1: A reverse Carnot cycle and Heat pump principle diagram

A heat pump transfers heat from a low-temperature source to a high-temperature sink using mechanical work. The process operates in a continuous cycle involving four main components, as shown in Figure 3.1. First, the evaporator absorbs heat from the low-temperature source, causing the refrigerant to evaporate into a low-pressure vapor. This vapor is then compressed by the compressor, which increases its pressure and temperature. Next, the high-pressure vapor releases its heat to the high-temperature sink in the condenser, where it condenses back into a liquid. Finally, the expansion valve reduces the pressure of the liquid, cooling it down and preparing it to re-enter the evaporator. This cycle repeats as long as the compressor is powered, effectively moving heat from a cooler area to a warmer one.

When considering the Carnot cycle operating between two reservoirs, one at a lower temperature T_L and another at a higher temperature T_H , the cycle's coefficient of performance (COP) is

outlined in Eq 3.1.

The temperature differential between the two reservoirs is $T_H - T_L = \Delta T_{\text{lift}}$, thus defining the COP of the Carnot cycle as the ratio of the temperature of the warmer reservoir to the temperature lift. It is evident from the equation that a greater ΔT results in a reduced $\text{COP}_{\text{Carnot}}$; conversely, a higher T_H enhances the $\text{COP}_{\text{Carnot}}$.

$$\text{COP}_{\text{ca}} = \frac{T_H}{T_H - T_L} \quad (3.1)$$

Stages in Simple Heat Pump Cycle, heat load and work in the system:

1. Compression:

$$\dot{W}_{\text{is}} = \dot{m}_R \cdot (h_2 - h_1) \quad (3.2)$$

The actual work done by the compressor, accounting for isentropic efficiency (η_{is}), is calculated using:

$$\dot{W}_{\text{Comp}} = \frac{\dot{W}_{\text{is}}}{\eta_{\text{is}}} = \frac{\dot{m}_R \cdot (h_2 - h_1)}{\eta_{\text{is}}} \quad (2.1) \quad (3.3)$$

2. Isobaric Heat Rejection in Condenser:

$$Q_E = \dot{m}_R \cdot (h_1 - h_4) \quad (3.4)$$

$$Q_C = \dot{W}_{\text{Comp}} + Q_E = \dot{m}_R \cdot (h_2 - h_3) \quad (3.5)$$

3. Isenthalpic Expansion:

$$h_4 = h_3 \quad (3.6)$$

4. Isobaric Heat Absorption:

$$Q_E = \dot{m}_R \cdot (h_1 - h_4) = U \cdot A \cdot \text{LMTD}_{\text{Heat-exchanger}} = \dot{V} \cdot \rho \cdot C_p \cdot \Delta T_{\text{Heat-source}} \quad (3.7)$$

$$\text{LMTD} = \frac{\Delta T_1 - \Delta T_2}{\ln\left(\frac{\Delta T_1}{\Delta T_2}\right)} \quad (3.8)$$

3.2 Cycle Configuration

Most heat pumps (HPs) typically operate on a subcritical vapor compression cycle, which involves rejecting heat below the refrigerant's critical temperature and pressure, leading to condensation. This process is illustrated in the pressure-enthalpy (P-h) diagram (Figure 3.3). On the other hand, a transcritical cycle involves heat rejection at pressures above the refrigerant's critical pressure through sensible cooling of a single supercritical phase in a gas cooler, instead of using a condenser [1].

Figure 3.2: Single stage: P-h diagram

Figure 3.3: Single stage: principle diagram

One significant advantage of heat rejection in the supercritical region is that it decouples the outlet temperature and pressure of the gas cooler (Figure 3.4, 3.5), offering two degrees of freedom as opposed to the single degree within the two-phase envelope. This feature allows for greater optimization possibilities within the system. By utilizing the properties of the refrigerant in the supercritical phase, the transcritical cycle enhances efficiency and flexibility.

For industrial applications, usually a higher output temperature is expected from the heat pump, which requires a higher compression ratio. The coefficient of performance of the cycle depends on the thermodynamic properties of the working fluid, the cycle configuration, the components, the stages of compression, the required temperature glide in the heat sink, etc. There are two cycle temperature profiles in a heat pump system to match the sink temperature requirement: Carnot and Lorentzen cycles.

While the Carnot cycle operates between constant temperatures T_H and T_L , the Lorenz cycle can be conceptualized as a sequence of Carnot cycles. COP is determined by substituting T_H in Eq. (3.1) with the logarithmic mean temperature of the gas cooler and evaporator inlet and outlet temperatures.

Figure 3.4: CO₂ heat pump Transcritical and subcritical P-h diagram

Figure 3.5: T-S diagram of gas cooler with pinch

$$\text{COP}_{\text{Lorenz}} = \frac{T_{\text{log,mean,gascooler}}}{T_{\text{log,mean,gascooler}} - T_{\text{log,mean,evaporator}}}$$

If the glide needed for heating and cooling both are small, an isothermal Carnot cycle is efficient as cycle loss due to temperature mismatch, as shown in Figure 3.6, the left Carnot cycle. In contrast, for a larger glide, a transcritical cycle is more efficient than a Carnot cycle; this transcritical cycle is also called the Lorentzen cycle. Propane (R-290) and Butane (R-600) are working fluids that operate similar to a Carnot cycle, whereas CO₂ (R-744) can operate in a transcritical cycle and is similar to a Carnot cycle.

Figure 3.6: Varying temperature glide influence in Carnot and Lorentzen cycle

3.3 High-Temperature Heat Pump

A high-temperature heat pump (HTHP) is a heat pump system that recovers heat from a specific temperature and upgrades it to a higher level using high-quality energy sources, such as electricity or heat from even higher temperatures. These pumps are distinguished by their ability to deliver output temperatures above 100°C. For example, an HTHP can heat water from 80°C to 120°C. They are predominantly used in commercial and industrial applications, where heating capacities exceed 100 kW [95].

A significant number of studies on HTHP cycles have been performed throughout the decades with advanced energy-efficient solutions. The relevant energy-efficient technologies that have been considered for the development of the heat pump model presented in this thesis are discussed here.

- **Internal Heat Exchanger**

The internal heat exchanger (IHEX) enhances heat pump efficiency by subcooling the liquid refrigerant and superheating the gas before it enters the compressor. This dual action reduces expansion losses and improves system thermodynamics [42]. By subcooling the refrigerant before the expansion valve, the IHEX minimizes flash gas formation, leading to more effective expansion and performance (Figure 3.7, 3.8). Superheating the gas entering the compressor reduces its density, thereby lowering the compressor's workload and energy consumption [28].

The IHEX also addresses practical issues by reducing risks associated with thermostatic expansion valves, such as liquid accumulation in the suction pipeline. It is particularly beneficial when the evaporator is higher than the condenser or when there is a significant distance between the evaporator and compressor. In these scenarios, the IHEX maintains temperature balance by subcooling the high-pressure liquid and superheating the gas, ensuring efficient operation despite distance or elevation differences.

However, the IHEX introduces certain trade-offs. While it reduces expansion losses, it increases superheat losses and compressor work due to the higher inlet gas temperature. The capacity of the IHEX is described by the formula:

$$\dot{Q}_{\text{IHEX}} = \dot{m}_R \cdot (h_3 - h_4) = \dot{m}_R \cdot (h_1 - h_6) \text{ (kJ/s)}$$

Figure 3.7: Principle sketch of heat pump with internal heat exchanger

Figure 3.8: Log P - h diagram of internal heat exchanger feature in Heat pump system

• Multistage Heat Pumps

High-temperature lifts in heat pumps, particularly in multi-stage configurations, are essential for various industrial applications. These high lifts result in high-pressure ratios, which can lead to increased compression work and high discharge temperatures on the high-pressure side of the compressor. Such high discharge temperatures may cause the dissolution of oil/working fluid, leading to lubrication issues and increased mechanical wear, especially in the compressor [2]. This can lower the system's lifetime and might lead to breakdowns. As the pressure ratio increases, isentropic efficiency and overall system performance decrease due to higher compressor and expansion losses [12].

To mitigate these issues, the process can be divided into separate steps. Common

methods to improve system performance include inter-cooling, using an economizer, cascade heat pump, subcooling, and internal heat exchanger [11]. Although these advanced configurations enhance system performance, they also increase investment costs. For heat pump cycles with two-stage compression and expansion, the intermediate pressure is often defined by

$$p_m = \sqrt{p_E \cdot p_C}$$

This method reduces the discharge temperature of the high-pressure compressor [6].

Figure 3.9: Principle sketch of Open intercooler with two-stage compression

Figure 3.10: Log P - h diagram of open intercooler two-stage compression

- **Open Intercooling**

Open intercooling is a method designed to enhance the performance of heat pump systems

by implementing a two-step compression and expansion process. This technique involves an intermediate pressure vessel where the discharge gas from the low-pressure compressor is cooled down by the expanded working fluid from the condenser. The working fluid is then expanded again from the intermediate pressure to the evaporation pressure.

This method offers several advantages, including:

- **Decreased Compression Losses:** By splitting the compression process into two stages, the compression ratio for each compressor is reduced, resulting in lower compression losses.
- **Lower Expansion Losses:** The two-step expansion process minimizes expansion losses, thereby improving overall efficiency.
- **Reduced Discharge Temperature:** Cooling the discharge gas between compression stages reduces the discharge temperature of the working fluid, mitigating the risk of thermal degradation of the working fluid and lubricants [69].

There are two types of open intercooling systems: full and partial. In full intercooling, the discharge gas from the first compressor stage is cooled completely to saturation, while in partial intercooling, it is only partially cooled. The effectiveness of these systems can be visualized using system sketches and pH-diagrams, as shown in various studies [7]. The incorporation of intercooling without heat recovery, although beneficial in reducing discharge temperature and improving efficiency, must be evaluated carefully as it can affect the overall heating performance of the system [10].

3.4 Sea Water as Heat Source

Norway's coastline, including all fjords and inlets, is approximately 55,000 km long. Norway's fifteen largest cities, as well as many towns and other settlements, are located along the coast with the possibility of using seawater as a heat source in heat pumps installed in homes, larger buildings, and district heating networks. The Gulf Stream ensures that the seawater temperature along the Norwegian coast is relatively high all year round. At a depth of 25 meters along the Norwegian coast, the minimum and maximum temperatures vary between 3–5°C and 9–15°C, respectively. In fjords, there may be significant deviations from the temperature conditions in coastal waters. A common feature of Norwegian fjords is that they are relatively deep, and many fjords are so-called threshold fjords. In threshold fjords, the temperature of the deep water within the threshold is relatively constant throughout the year [70].

The Norwegian coast benefits from the Gulf Stream, hosting numerous large-scale properties near its shores. The country's extensive coastline allows for the prevalent use of seawater as a heat source for large heat pumps. In Norway, seawater temperatures, typically ranging from 3 to 15°C, exhibit less variation compared to ambient air temperatures [19].

Figure 3.11: Seawater heat pump systems: (A) Direct, (B) and (C) Indirect, drawn with inspiration from Brækken and Sannan [19]

In Trøndelag, Orkanger stands out as a key industrial hub surrounded by Orkdalsfjorden, where seawater temperatures peak at about 14.1°C in August and drop to around 5.4°C in March, as shown in Figure 3.12. Seawater heat pump technology (SWHP) proves vital, particularly in winter when heating demands surge and seawater maintains a relatively stable temperature due to its depth, less affected by surface conditions [84]. SWHPs, leveraging the minimal seasonal

temperature shifts and higher energy efficiency, function through either open-loop systems, directly drawing water, or closed-loop systems, circulating water within a contained circuit in the water body [65].

Figure 3.12: Orkanger monthly average surface water temperature, Data source (SeaTemperature.org 2023)

As illustrated in Figure 3.11, SWHP systems vary: direct systems (A) circulate seawater through corrosion-resistant titanium evaporators, while indirect systems (B and C) use a secondary brine circuit to prevent seawater contact with the evaporator, necessitating regular maintenance to prevent fouling [19].

3.4.1 Material Selection for HEX Against Seawater Corrosion

One of the primary challenges for SWHP involves selecting materials for components that are in direct contact with surface water, such as pumps and heat exchangers, due to the salt content in seawater. The salt can cause corrosion of components through an electrochemical corrosion process, which accelerates at higher temperatures [56].

For pumps, when dealing with higher velocity, coupling SS316L with a more anodic sacrificial material is recommended for impellers, shrouds, and casings. Titanium and Monel are also noted for their resistance to seawater corrosion and have excellent erosion resistance [56].

For heat exchangers, recent studies consistently favor titanium because of its outstanding resistance to galvanic corrosion, a finding first documented by Kinelski [44]. Initial evaluations included materials like AL-6X stainless steel, 90/10 cupro-nickel alloy, and aluminum; however, these were deemed less effective mainly due to their susceptibility to corrosion in marine

Figure 3.13: 3D representation of Titanium plate heat exchanger

environments [56]. Carbon steel was dismissed early in the selection process because of its severe corrosion issues. Moreover, while copper alloys and stainless steel 316 do offer some resistance to corrosion, their effectiveness significantly declines at higher flow velocities, specifically beyond 1-3 meters per second. Echoing these findings, Smebye, Midttømme, and Stene [70] advocate for using titanium in seawater systems and high alloy steel in freshwater systems, emphasizing the importance of material selection based on the specific environmental context.

3.5 Choice of Natural Working Fluids

The choice of working fluid is one of the most important aspects for hot water and steam generation heat pump systems. Working fluids like R717 (Ammonia), Water (R718), CO₂ (R744), and hydrocarbons (HC) are gaining attention due to their critical temperatures—the highest temperature at which they can be condensed under pressure. A higher critical temperature of the refrigerant allows more efficient heat pump operation with a high-temperature heat output.

Here’s a quick overview of natural and hydrocarbon working fluids and their selected thermodynamic properties:

Type	Working Fluid	Description	T _{crit} (°C)	p _{crit} (bar)	ODP (-)	GWP (-)	SG
Natural	R-718	Water	373.9	220.6	0	0	A1
Natural	R-717	Ammonia	132.3	113.3	0	0	B2L
Natural	R-744	Carbon dioxide	31.0	73.8	0	1	A1
HC	R-601	n-Pentane	196.6	33.7	0	5	A3
HC	R-601a	Isopentane	187.8	33.8	0	4	A3
HC	R-600	n-Butane	152.0	38.0	0	4	A3
HC	R-600a	Isobutane	134.7	36.3	0	3	A3
HC	R-290	Propane	96.7	42.5	0	3	A3

Table 3.1: Thermodynamic properties of working fluids: hydrocarbon and natural

Carbon Dioxide:

Carbon dioxide (R744) is a well-suited working fluid for many heat pump and refrigeration applications due to its excellent thermophysical properties, low global warming potential (GWP = 1), and zero ozone depletion potential (ODP). CO₂ heat pumps exhibit low pressure ratios, enhancing compressor efficiencies and heat transfer properties. With a critical temperature of 31.1°C and a critical pressure of 73.8 bar, CO₂ systems often operate in a trans-critical process, where the condenser is replaced with a gas cooler [57]. The high-pressure levels in trans-critical CO₂ systems offer advantages such as high energy density and volumetric heating capacity (VHC), leading to smaller component sizes [67]. However, CO₂’s performance can be lower for high heat sink inlet temperatures (HSiIT) due to its dependence on increased sub-cooling. Despite this, CO₂ is particularly effective for heat pumps with stable heat source temperatures and large temperature glides at the heat sink, such as domestic hot water heat pumps [50].

While the high operating pressures of CO₂ systems require robust designs, their efficiency and environmental benefits make them a compelling choice for modern applications [62].

Ammonia:

Ammonia (R717) has a critical temperature of 132.3°C and exhibits favorable thermodynamic properties, making it a prominent choice in high-temperature heat pump applications. Its high specific heat capacity and heat transfer coefficient enhance its attractiveness for industrial applications. Additionally, ammonia is more cost-effective compared to fluorocarbon refrigerants, further increasing its industrial appeal [57]. Ammonia is environmentally friendly, with zero ozone depletion potential (ODP) and a high volumetric cooling capacity, which contributes to its efficiency in industrial settings [22]. However, it is worth noting that ammonia is toxic and flammable, necessitating careful handling and specific safety measures in its application [62]. Despite these challenges, the advantages of ammonia as a refrigerant, particularly in terms of cost and environmental impact, make it a viable option for many industrial processes [73].

Water:

Water (R718) is an excellent working fluid for heat pump applications due to its high latent heat of evaporation and superior heat transfer properties, including a high isobaric specific heat capacity (C_p 4.2 kJ/kg·K) [57]. It is cost-effective, readily accessible, and environmentally friendly, with zero ozone depletion potential (ODP) and low global warming potential (GWP) [34]. However, its high specific volume and low-pressure evaporation under atmospheric conditions limit its suitability for low-temperature applications in vapor compression heat pumps (VCHP) [62]. Water and steam, however, can deliver high-temperature heat up to 200°C through mechanical vapor recompression using oil-free steam compressors, which eliminate lubrication issues found in traditional compressors [92]. Despite some limitations, water's unique properties and environmental benefits make it valuable for specific heat pump and high-temperature applications.

Hydrocarbons:

The hydrocarbons n-butane (R-600) and pentane (R-601) are notable working fluids due to their high critical temperatures of 152°C and 196.6°C, respectively, with pressures of 38.0 bar and 33.7 bar. These fluids exhibit no ozone depletion potential (ODP) and very low global warming potential (GWP), making them environmentally favorable choices [22]. n-Butane and pentane have high specific heat capacities, contributing to their excellent thermal properties and efficiency in heat pump applications. Despite these advantages, their high flammability

requires stringent safety regulations, as outlined in EN 378-1:2016, which limits the refrigerant charge to 2.5 kg in monitored commercial settings with explosion protection [62]. Pentane, in particular, has gained prominence in steam production systems due to its high efficiency and superior thermal properties [57]. While safety concerns necessitate careful handling, the performance benefits and low environmental impact of these hydrocarbons make them viable options in specific industrial applications [73].

3.6 Absorption Compression Heat Pump

The Absorption Compression Heat Pump (ACHP) utilizes zeotropic mixtures as working fluids, blending features of both absorption and vapor compression heat pumps [64, 5]. The first patent of the ACHP cycle was named after its inventor Osenbrück [61]. In this system, the working fluid is a mix of a refrigerant and an absorbent, differentiated by their wide-boiling properties, rather than using pure substances [58].

Significantly, the ACHP system is designed to optimize heat management by tailoring the concentration and flow rate of the working fluid to meet specific heat source and sink requirements. This innovative approach not only decreases the necessary compression ratio compared to traditional Vapor Compression Heat Pumps (VCHP), but also allows the system to reach high sink temperatures over 100°C , maintaining a high coefficient of performance (COP). Such capabilities make the ACHP system highly suitable for various industrial applications where high-temperature heat is essential [5].

Figure 3.14: Schematics of basic absorption compression heat pump cycle

Figure 3.14 illustrates a basic sketch of an absorption compression cycle. This cycle utilizes an NH_3 -Water mixture, which consists of two concentrations known as 'lean' and 'rich'. At the desorber inlet, the mixture presents as a two-phase solution (7). Here, NH_3 starts to evaporate as the heat source increases the solution's temperature, leading to a decrease in ammonia concentration within the solution (8). This solution is then collected in the separator, where it's divided into an ammonia-lean (9) solution and low-pressure vapor (1). The low-pressure vapor undergoes compression, resulting in higher temperature and pressure (2). Concurrently, a solution pump raises the pressure of the lean solution correspondingly (10 to 3).

An internal heat exchanger cools the rich solution from the absorber before it's expanded into the desorber (5 to 6). Meanwhile, the lean solution absorbs heat from the rich solution stream (10 to 3). The superheated NH_3 vapor and lean solution are mixed (3) at the absorber's inlet. In the absorber, the vapor is absorbed by the lean solution, and the generated heat is transferred to the sink. As absorption continues at the outlet of the desorber (5), the rich solution enters the internal heat exchanger and is throttled down to the desorber (7) at a lower pressure and temperature, thereby completing the cycle.

3.6.1 Zeotropic Mixture

Ammonia and water mixed zeotropic mixture refrigerant with different boiling points exhibit temperature glide during isobaric phase change. Zeotropic mixtures follow a non-isothermal Lorenz cycle during heat rejection and absorption rather than the Carnot cycle [39].

This non-isothermal heat rejection and absorption follow a 'temperature glide' and can be adjusted by controlling the mixture concentration and circulation ratio, which allows the heat pump cycle to match the heat source and sink conditions [26].

Using a zeotropic mixture, heat pumps can operate more efficiently and need not have as high a pressure ratio compared to heat pump systems using a conventional vapor compression heat pump cycle with a single fluid [5].

However, designing the desorber and absorber due to the non-linear properties of the ammonia/water mixture during phase change processes needs extra consideration [58].

3.6.2 Features of ACHP Cycle

Using an ammonia absorption compression heat pump exhibits a number of thermodynamic advantages and degrees of flexibility compared to conventional vapor compression heat pumps [58, 39].

Due to the absorption of ammonia, condensing pressure can be reduced by changing the weight

% of ammonia with a higher condensing temperature. Saturation pressure can be altered by changing the average composition of the solution at a constant temperature circulating at the absorber and desorber. Also, the phase changes in the absorber and desorber are non-isothermal, which gives another degree of flexibility to achieve temperature glide and match with source and sink temperature by varying the composition changes of the liquid and vapor phases [58].

Jensen [39] suggests that the circulation ratio (CR) and the rich ammonia mass fraction are two additional degrees of freedom compared to conventional vapor compression heat pumps (VCHP), and CR is defined by the following formula:

$$CR = \frac{\dot{m}_{lean}}{\dot{m}_{rich}} \quad (3.9)$$

And ammonia mass fraction can be defined by the following equation:

$$x_r = \frac{m_{ammonia}}{m_{water}} \quad (3.10)$$

The ammonia mass fraction of the lean solution can be controlled by circulation ratio, thus the necessary temperature glide can be achieved accordingly [5]. As referred to in section 3.6.1, a zeotropic mixture follows the Lorenz cycle, therefore the theoretical limit value for the coefficient of performance can be calculated as proposed by [51].

$$COP_{Lorenz} = \frac{T_{log,mean,sink}}{T_{log,mean,sink} - T_{log,mean,source}} \quad (3.11)$$

The corresponding logarithmic temperature can be found using the equation below:

$$T_{log,mean} = \frac{T_{secondary\ fluid,in} - T_{secondary\ fluid,out}}{\ln\left(\frac{T_{secondary\ fluid,in}}{T_{secondary\ fluid,out}}\right)} \quad (3.12)$$

Ahrens [4] summarized that ACHP can achieve higher sink temperatures over VCHP cycles with pure ammonia with lower vapor discharge pressure and reduced pressure ratio.

3.7 Literature Review on HTHP for Steam Generation

High-temperature heat pumps (HTHPs) using hydrocarbon and natural refrigerants have advanced significantly over recent decades, showcasing improvements in efficiency and capacity across steam generation technologies.

3.7.1 Hydrocarbon-Based Heat Pumps

Yamazaki and Kubo [89] pioneered the development of an R601 single-stage heat pump, achieving a condensation temperature of 130°C with a COP of 4.5 and a heating capacity of 400 kW using a screw compressor at an 80-90°C source temperature. Building on this, Kimura et al. [43] introduced an R600 transcritical cycle HTHP in collaboration with Mayekawa and Waseda University. Their system utilized waste heat around 80°C, achieving a COP of 3.5 to heat oil from 80°C to 180°C with a 300 kW capacity using oil-free centrifugal compressors. However, the flammable nature of R-600 (Butane) necessitated special safety measures such as proper ventilation.

Similarly, Wemmers et al. [86] demonstrated the potential of a butane heat pump for producing low-pressure steam (up to 120°C) from waste heat in paper machine hoods. This system provided a heat output of 160 kW with a COP of 1.9 and included a subcooler to heat process water to 70°C. Further advancements were made by Bamigbetan et al. [14] in a collaborative project between NTNU and SINTEF, Norway. They developed a cascade HTHP using butane (R600) as the high-side fluid and propane (R290) as the low-side fluid. Their system achieved a sink temperature of up to 115°C with an average COP of 3.1 for a 58-72K temperature lift.

Mayekawa further advanced hydrocarbon-based HTHPs by developing heat pump packages capable of supplying hot brine up to 120°C using R-600, with a COP range of 3.2 to 4.8 and a heating capacity of 750 kW. Additionally, their R-601 (n-pentane) system generated steam up to 145°C with a heating capacity of 1000 kW and a COP of 2.6. Moreover, InterHeat is working on two HTHP projects using R600a and R601a, aiming to achieve up to 160°C by 2025 [95].

3.7.2 Other Natural Refrigerant-Based Heat Pumps

Tveit [80] developed an industrial HTHP using helium (R704), capable of producing steam up to 10 bar (184°C) for dairy processing, with a COP of 2.1 and a heat capacity of 449 kW. Similarly, Chamoun et al. [24] achieved a condensation temperature of 145°C using water (R718) in a pilot plant, with a heat capacity of 380 kW and a COP of 5.5. Madsboell, Weel, and Kolstrup [52] also contributed by developing a water (R718) vapor single-stage compression HTHP for industrial heating needs of 90-110°C, with a heat capacity range of 100-500 kW.

De Larminat et al. [27] designed an R718 HTHP prototype, achieving a COP of 5.5 at an evaporation temperature of 90°C and a condensation temperature of 130°C, further highlighting the potential of water-based refrigerants.

3.7.3 Ammonia-Based Heat Pumps

Ammonia-based systems have also been explored extensively. Sang, Xu, and Yu [66] tested an NH₃ two-stage compression system capable of delivering temperatures up to 87°C, with a COP ranging from 2.75 to 3.49 depending on the evaporation temperature. Wu et al. [88] developed an NH₃-H₂O absorption compression heat pump (ACHP), showing that reducing the generator inlet temperature from 130°C to 115°C caused the COP to decrease from 1.442 to 1.271, with a significant drop in heating capacity.

Jensen et al. [37] implemented an NH₃-H₂O ACHP in a spray-drying facility, achieving optimal COPs of 4.0 and 3.5 under varying conditions, influenced by factors such as ammonia mass fraction, circulation ratio, and heat load recovery from exhaust air.

3.7.4 Carbon Dioxide-Based Heat Pumps

Cao, Ye, and Wang [23] investigated an R744 transcritical cycle HTHP, demonstrating that using an internal heat exchanger optimized discharge pressure, leading to COP improvements from 2.51 to 2.91. Additionally, Zühlsdorf et al. [94] experimented with an R717 multistage compression cycle combined with an R600 bottom cycle and an R744 reverse Brayton cycle, achieving a maximum temperature of 210°C and an overall COP of 1.9.

Heat Pump Cycle, Compressor Refrigerant	Heating Capacity (kW)	COP (source/sink temperature °C)	Reference
HTHP, screw R601 (pentane)	400	4.5 (80/130)	[89]
Transcritical HTHP, centrifugal R600 (butane)	300	3.5 (80/180)	[43]
HTHP + IHX + subcooler, piston R600 (butane)	160	1.9 (60/125)	[86]
HTHP cascade + IHX R290/R600 (propane/butane)	20	2.1 (25/115)	[14]
Single Stage + IHX + R600+ Piston	20~40	n.a. (20/110)	[40]
3 compression stages R718 + R600, R744	-	3.4 (125/140)	[94]
Piston compressor+ R600	750	4.8 (72/120)	[95]
Screw compressor+ R601	1000	2.6 (90/145)	[95]
3 Stage Turbo + R600	300	3.5 (80/180)	[95]
HC cascade, R600a + R601a, Screw compressor	500	n.a. (120/160)	[95]
HC cascade, R718 + R600, Screw compressor	1000	n.a. (120/160)	[95]
VHTHP + flash tank, twin-screw R718 (water)	285	6.10 (85/117), 1.96 (85/150)	[87]
HTHP (reversed Stirling cycle), piston R704 (helium)	449	2.1 (85/183)	[80]
HTHP + flash tank, twin-screw R718 (water)	380	5.5 (94/121)	[24]
Single Stage+ R718+ Centrifugal Compression	100~500	n.a. (90/110)	[52]
Single Stage + IHX + R744+ Piston	35~60	2.91 (10/90)	[23]
Two stage+ R718+ Centrifugal	700	5.5 (90/130)	[40]
Two stage+ R717+ Twin Screw	1147~1618	3.49 (25/85)	[40]
ACHP+ NH ₃ -H ₂ O	20~70	4.5 (-10/130)	[88]
ACHP+ NH ₃ -H ₂ O	432	5.3 (80/144.5)	[38]

Table 3.2: Summary of cycle, heating capacity, sink outlet of natural working fluid SGHP systems

3.8 Theory of Steam Generation by Heat Pump

In Steam Generation Heat Pumps (SGHPs), steam can be produced by either direct heating of pressurized water or flashing pressurized hot water [83].

Direct Steam Production:

In direct steam production, pressurized water is heated until it evaporates. If superheated steam is needed, additional heat is supplied. Due to the significant density difference between liquid and vapor phases, extremely large heat pump condensers would be necessary. To avoid this, integrating the Vapor Compression Heat Pump (VCHP) in a boiler is a potential solution. In this setup, saturated steam is extracted at the boiler's top while feed water is supplied at the bottom. Boiler temperature is controlled by regulating steam pressure.

Figure 3.15: Steam generation path

Steam Flashing:

SGHPs also produce steam through a flashing process. In this method, the VCHP heats pressurized water, which is then flashed to a liquid-vapor mixture in a flash tank. A fraction of the water becomes steam, which is extracted at the tank's top, while the remaining water is collected and recirculated to the condenser by a pump. This process avoids the disadvantage of large condensers.

For MVR systems, all common types of compressors can be utilized. Rotary blowers or axial or centrifugal fans are preferred for small temperature and pressure lifts, whereas higher

temperature lifts require axial and centrifugal compressors. Piston compressors are used for very large lifts [45].

Steam Generation Path and Equation

The steam-generation path is a steady flow process in an open system, typically in heat exchangers, where steam properties remain constant within any control volume. This process can be classified into two types: pressurization on the liquid side and on the vapor side [90].

If an MVR is used after the evaporation process at the heat exchanger's high heating side, the total work input can be calculated as follows:

$$W_{\text{total}} = W_{\text{HP}} + W_c \quad (3.13)$$

The heat output from the total path is:

$$Q_{\text{total}} = \dot{m}_v \cdot (h_B - h_A) \quad (3.14)$$

Figure 3.16: Steam generation System Sketch

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For the bottom cycle, corresponding to heat pump work and the MVR compressor work input:

$$W_{\text{HP}} = \dot{m}_v \times \frac{(h_{\text{im}} - h_A)}{COP_{T_a \rightarrow T_{\text{im}}}} \quad (3.15)$$

$$W_C = \dot{m}_v \times \frac{(h_{B, \text{is}} - h_{\text{im}})}{\eta_{\text{is}}} \quad (3.16)$$

Finally, the steam generation system efficiency can be calculated by:

$$\eta_{\text{steam.generation}} = \frac{Q_{\text{total}}}{W_{\text{HP}} + W_C} \quad (3.17)$$

4 Preliminary Work and System Description

In this section, the existing thermal energy demand of the poultry processing plant is considered as the foundation, and the current configuration of the energy system is outlined. The main motivation behind studying the existing energy system is to develop the concept of utilizing excess heat, which would be upgraded by a cascaded high-temperature heat pump system. To achieve this, it is necessary to first investigate the current thermal demand, the dimensions of the system, and the dynamics of the refrigeration system.

4.1 Energy Central Configuration

The poultry processing plant presented here is part of master student Eirik Svendsen's thesis [75], where he investigated cold thermal storage in relation to freezing, air conditioning, and cooling demand for Norsk Kylling, a meat processing plant. The meat processing plant is located in Orkland municipality, a key industrial hub in Trøndelag county, Norway, by the Orkdalsfjorden, a side fjord of Trondheimsfjorden in Orkland and Skaun municipalities in Trøndelag. The seawater functions as a sink to condense the ammonia in the upper refrigeration cycles, as discussed in the following sections. The warm water is then returned to the sea after condensation. The seawater temperatures peak at about 14.1°C in August and drop to around 5.4°C in March, as shown in Figure 3.12.

In this study, the scope of energy central operability has been extended from cold energy demand to hot energy demand, which includes hot water production and steam generation using high-temperature heat pump cycles.

Understanding the current refrigeration demand is crucial to establish the foundation and set the boundary conditions. This understanding is essential for upgrading the waste heat source for hot water and steam production using cascaded high-temperature heat pump cycles.

4.2 Refrigeration System

The refrigeration system covers three different temperature levels: LT (freezing), MT (chilling), and AC (cooling of air). In addition to meeting cold thermal energy demand, the current refrigeration cycles produce hot water from desuperheater heat exchangers on the warm side of the cycle. A simplified P&ID of the system is presented in Figure 4.1, where a cascaded system includes CO₂ as the bottom cycle working fluid and NH₃ as the upper cycle working fluid.

Bottom Cycle

The bottom cycle consists of low-temperature and medium-temperature circuits, with working pressures of 10 bar and 30.5 bar, respectively. Vapor from the LT separator (working pressure: 10 bar) is superheated using an IHEX, and a bypass valve ensures the required superheating level is not exceeded. A group of three piston compressors withdraws the vapor, which is then condensed by three cascaded heat exchangers, transferring heat to the upper NH₃ cycle. The condensed vapor is collected in an MT separator (working pressure: 30.5 bar), and an expansion valve connected to the LT separator ensures both tanks have enough liquid to meet refrigeration demands.

Another two cascaded heat exchangers condense the generated vapor in the MT separator by transferring the heat to the upper NH₃ cycle. Liquid from the LT and MT separators is evaporated to supply the freezing and chilling circuits in the cold storage, production, and dispatch areas.

Upper Cycle

The upper cycle meets the air conditioning (AC) demand and extracts heat by condensing high-pressure CO₂ from both groups of cascaded heat exchangers in the bottom cycle. Evaporated NH₃ from the two groups of cascaded heat exchangers is collected in an LT separator (working pressure: 2.9 bar). A glycol circuit serves the AC consumers' demand, and the evaporated NH₃ from the glycol heat exchanger is collected in an MT separator. A portion of the liquid is further expanded to the LT separator to condense the bottom cycle high-pressure CO₂ in sub-critical operation.

The evaporated NH₃ from the AC circuit is compressed by a dedicated set of compressors. Another set of compressors is dedicated to withdrawing liquid from the LT separator of the NH₃ cycle. Compressed vapor from both groups of compressors is condensed through a group of three seawater condensers, dimensioned for a total capacity of 8500 kW. The condensed liquid is further throttled down to the AC separator tank and fed back to the MT separator tank.

The desuperheater of the upper cycle recovers heat from the MT and AC compressors' discharge lines and preheats water from 8°C to 70°C, with a capacity of 430 kW. This is achieved by two heat exchangers with an intermediate glycol circuit connected upstream of the condensers. Additionally, compressor heat is rejected into a motor cooling circuit, which can produce 50°C water.

Figure 4.1: Simplified P&ID for the refrigeration system at meat processing plant

Energy Circuit	Capacity [kW]	Refrigeration Demand
LT (-40°C)	1250	Freezing equipment and storage
MT (-5°C)	3250	Chilling equipment, storage, and production areas
AC (+4°C)	2600	Air cooling, washdown, and dehumidifying
Desuperheater	430	Pre-heats water from 8°C to 70°C
Motor Cooling	620	Pre-heats water from 8°C to 50°C
Condenser	8500	Condenses ammonia at 35°C using sea water (10°C to 22°C)

Table 4.1: Description of energy circuits in the refrigeration cycle

5 Methodology

This chapter outlines the procedure and methodology used in developing an extended version of the energy central. The focus is on the thermophysical advantages and financial comparisons of alternatives to generate steam and hot water for the process requirements, instead of using direct steam from fossil fuel-based steam boilers or electric steam boilers.

The ACHP, an ammonia absorption compression heat pump known as the “Osenbrück 4.0 Heat Pump,” was built in an NTNU lab funded by the ”ENOUGH” project. In this project, the ACHP is modeled and combined with a CO₂ or NH₃ cycle as a cascade system. The model configuration and component sizing are presented, along with the corresponding methodology. The experimental results are compared with the developed model to evaluate the system’s performance, followed by an economic analysis.

5.1 Integration of Heat Recovery HTHP

As depicted in Figure 3.12, the inlet temperature of the seawater varies seasonally, ranging from 5.4°C to 14.1°C. This variation causes fluctuations in the condenser’s heating capacity due to the changing temperature difference between the hot ammonia refrigerant and the cold seawater stream. Consequently, the seawater outlet temperature varies depending on the partial load or full load operation mode of the upper refrigeration cycle and the inlet water temperature (Figure 5.2).

Figure 5.1: Snippet of Energisentral control system of Norsk Kylling

Figure 5.2: Sectional P&ID of NH_3 refrigeration cycle

A snapshot taken at the end of April 2024 from the energy central control system (Figure 5.1) shows that seawater entering at 6.3°C exits at 15.1°C after condensing ammonia in three cascaded heat exchangers in the upper cycle refrigeration system and cooling the compressor oil. In a full load system, this outlet seawater temperature can reach $23\text{--}25^\circ\text{C}$. As discussed in Section 4.1, this waste heat, worth 8500 kW for a maximum mass flow of $612\text{ m}^3/\text{hr}$, is then sent back to Orkanger fjord.

Figure 5.3: T - S diagram for multilevel source heat upgrading

This heat can be further utilized by a high-temperature heat pump system to produce hot water and steam for meat processing and other auxiliary demands at a range of 90 to 120°C . Incorporating a cascaded high-temperature heat pump system in the energy central results in lower primary energy consumption compared to conventional methods of water heating and

Figure 5.4: Simplified principle diagram of proposed cascaded HTHP models

steam production, such as electric or steam boilers, as shown in Figure 5.3.

By incorporating an R744 (CO_2) or R717 (NH_3) cycle with a combination of ACHP systems, the meat processing plant can produce pressurized hot water or steam for their energy circuit with minimal work input in the compressors. In the R744 or R717 heat pump system, the seawater will be cooled down for an evaporator temperature of 10°C , and this surplus seawater heat will be upgraded to a 70°C sink outlet for a condensing temperature close to 80°C . Furthermore, the sink outlet of the bottom R744 or R717 cycle will be the source inlet for the proposed ACHP cycle, further upgraded to a sink outlet of 120°C or even higher based on process requirements. This sink outlet phase can be either steam or pressurized hot water.

To evaluate this concept, two alternative cascaded systems have been proposed in this study to harness this excess heat and are classified as two models, as illustrated in Figure 5.4.

5.1.1 System Description CA-1: Bottom Cycle

The proposed P&ID for the R717 bottom cycle, consisting of a two-stage open intercooler type system, is shown in Figure 5.5. The system absorbs seawater heat through an indirect titanium type plate heat exchanger (PHEX) to avoid corrosion in the evaporator, as discussed in Section 3.4.1. The condenser outlet seawater first warms cold city water through a titanium type PHEX, and a cold water storage tank stores this preheated cold city water. If the tank temperature falls below 11°C, Pump P01 recirculates the water through the second titanium PHEX and restores it in the tank. There is a common delivery line of cold city water from the tank to the evaporator and condenser of the R717 two-stage system, but with different pumps (P02 and P03) to control the mass flow based on load.

Figure 5.5: Piping and instrumentation diagram (P&ID) showing R717 open inter-cooler heat pump connected to sea water heat source. Blue lines are sea water and cold water; red lines are hot water; orange lines are high-pressure fluid pipes, green line are intermediate pressure fluid pipes and yellow lines are low-pressure fluid pipes

The heat pump unit comprises the following main components: flooded evaporator, separator, low and high-stage piston compressors, open flash intercooler, desuperheater, condenser, and throttling valves. The evaporation temperature is set to 10°C with a working pressure of 6.2 bar for a 5K approach temperature. The condenser's working pressure is 41.5 bar to achieve an

outlet temperature of 70°C from the sink. The evaporator, desuperheater, and condensers are fusion-bonded plate type heat exchangers. The desuperheater and condensers have controlled mass flow, and the desuperheater rejected heat to the city water is mixed with the condenser's outlet to reach a set temperature of 70°C. Three hot water storage tanks were integrated with this proposed system to store hot water at 70°C and refill based on demand of the top ACHP cycle.

Figure 5.6: Piping and instrumentation diagram (P&ID) showing R744 heat pump with IHEX connected to sea water heat source. Blue lines are sea water and cold water; red lines are hot water; orange lines are high-pressure fluid pipes, and yellow lines are low-pressure fluid pipes

5.1.2 System Description CA-2: Bottom Cycle

Another alternative proposal for the bottom cycle is the R744 heat pump with an IHEX solution, as presented in the P&ID and consisting of three gas coolers, as shown in Figure 5.6. The source inlet configuration is the same as proposed in the R717 cycle, except that a subcooler preheats the cold city water before it rejects heat to the evaporator. The main components include a direct expansion evaporator, separator, piston compressor, gas coolers, subcooler, suction gas heat exchanger, and throttling valves. The evaporation temperature is set at 10°C and 45.02 bar, whereas the gas cooler operates at 90 bar, controlled by a pressure-controlled valve. The

target sink outlet temperature of the gas cooler is 70°C for water, and three hot water storage tanks are integrated with this proposed system to store hot water at 70°C and refill based on the demand of the top ACHP cycle.

5.1.3 System Description CA-1 & CA-2: Top Cycle

The top cycle is an ammonia absorption compression heat pump (ACHP) system, utilizing a zeotropic mixture (ammonia and water) as the working fluid for the system. In the desorber, as shown in Figure 5.7, the ammonia-water mixture is in a two-phase region, and the concentration of ammonia decreases as it evaporates due to source heat. This process creates a lean ammonia-water mixture and ammonia vapor, which later feeds into the liquid separator. The liquid separator separates the two-phase mixture, and the ammonia vapor is compressed by an oil-free screw compressor. Meanwhile, the lean solution is pumped with the help of a solution pump and divided into two streams: one stream is injected into the screw compressor as a cooling medium, and the other stream passes through the IHX and enters the mixing point where compressed high-pressure ammonia vapor mixes with this lean solution.

This process involves the absorption of vapor ammonia into a high-pressure weak ammonia-water solution, generating heat that is rejected to the sink. At the absorber's outlet, the solution becomes a one-phase strong ammonia-water solution, which is collected in a high-pressure liquid receiver. This solution is then expanded to a low-pressure strong solution before entering the desorber inlet. A flash tank connected to the sink outlet produces steam from pressurized hot water at low pressure. The water pump is assumed to maintain the pressure difference of the hot water before and after flashing. A centrifugal fan can be incorporated at the steam outlet of the flash tank for a small pressure lift. For higher temperature lifts, axial and centrifugal compressors are used, while piston compressors are utilized for very large lifts [45].

Figure 5.7: Piping and instrumentation diagram (P&ID) showing ACHP oil free system connected to bottom cycle (R744 or R717). Blue lines are warm water from bottom cycle; red lines are hot water or steam; yellow lines are lean solution fluid pipes, green line are vapor flow and orange lines are rich solution fluid pipes

5.2 Experimental ACHP Setup

An experimental prototype named “*Osenbrück 4.0 Heat Pump*” was constructed in an NTNU laboratory to investigate the performance of an ACHP cycle. The test rig facility features an oil-free twin screw compressor system designed to optimize various component parameters, including variations in heat source and sink circuit input parameters. This setup aims to explore oil-free compression technology for high-temperature industrial applications.

Figure 5.8: Schematic of liquid injection line in the screw compressor, drawn with inspiration from Ahrens [4]

The screw compressor operates without oil to reduce costs and complexity, using liquid injection for cooling and lubrication. As shown in Figure 5.8, liquid is injected through three ports. The first port injects lean solution from the solution pump outlet onto the bearings and into the compression chamber at the start of the compression process, serving as the main injection for this study. The remaining two ports inject lean solution into the male and female rotor cavities of the compressor. The experimental work focused on observing the impact of injecting lean/weak solution into the compressor for sealing, cooling, and lubrication.

Figure 5.9 illustrates the simplified process flow diagram (P&ID), including the components and the pressurized water auxiliary system. The main components are brazed plate heat exchangers, which function as the absorber, desorber, and IHX. The setup also includes a twin screw compressor, a solution pump, two separator tanks, an expansion valve, and an auxiliary system for sink and source supply. The key components and their specifications are presented in Appendix D, Table D.1.

Figure 5.9: Simple P&ID of “Osenbrück 4.0 Heat Pump” setup at NTNU

Figure 5.10: Photograph of the test unit, 1: denotes vapor suction to compressor, 2 denotes discharge line from compressor, 9" denotes injection ports, 3" denotes mixing unit, LPR is Separator tank at low pressure

5.3 Case Scenario

To evaluate the performance of the extended energy system, a thermal demand profile for hot water and steam use is needed as input for the simulation model. Due to limited information on the thermal demand profile, an assumption-based scenario was created to develop a simplified model. This model can later be customized based on actual demand data.

To analyze the thermal demand profile during production and non-production hours, a duration curve was constructed (see Figure 5.12). This curve maps the specific thermal demand in relation to the production hours. It is assumed that thermal demands start before production begins and end after production, with a gradual increase or decrease in the curve. A 24-hour timescale was chosen, assuming production hours are from 8:00 AM to 3:00 PM, followed by post-production cleaning from 4:00 PM to 8:00 PM.

Figure 5.11: Thermal demand profile for a 24 hours period

To prepare for production, processes such as water pre-heating, warm water utilities, chilling, and freezing are started before the first poultry or bird is processed, that's why the supply to thermal demand starts at 7 AM.

Since the extended energy system's ability to produce hot water and steam solely depends on the condenser capacity of the ammonia refrigeration cycle, understanding the demand curve of the ammonia refrigeration cycle is crucial. The air conditioning (AC) demand is assumed to be constant during production but increases significantly at the end of production for storage (1:00

PM to 5:00 PM) and maintains a constant demand for dehumidification of the production area. This cooling demand is managed by the upper NH₃ cycle in the current refrigeration system, as outlined in Section 4.2.

While the process steam demand starts at the beginning of production and stops at the end, steam is still used to meet the thermal demand for hot water production for cleaning. The hot water demand curve reflects the need for source water preparation for the absorption chiller heat pump (ACHP) cycle to produce steam, as well as for cleaning and other process requirements.

During non-production hours, it is assumed that the demand for 70°C hot water for utility and residential purposes of the facility is 30 kW. During production hours, this demand increases to 626 kW and falls to 476.98 kW during cleaning hours. The hot water at 70°C is utilized as a supply for the ACHP sink and source inlet during production hours.

A heat load of 610 kW is designed from the bottom cycle of the cascaded system. The ACHP system is assumed to produce both pressurized hot water and steam. The demand for pressurized hot water is set at 50% of the mass flow of steam for different demand profiles throughout the production hour, resulting in a pressurized hot water heat load of 105 kW, which reduces to 52.5 kW at 120°C.

The demand for steam is 1300 kW and 700 kW throughout the period, with varying steam outlet temperatures and pressures.

5.4 Modeling Tools

The proposed heat pump cycles (R744, R717, ACHP) were modeled using the object-oriented, equation-based, open-source modeling language Modelica. Dynamic simulation models of these heat pump cycles were developed using Dymola 2020x [76] and the TLK-Thermo GmbH refrigerant and component libraries [78]. Basic components used in the simulation models, such as heat exchangers, compressors, separators, expansion valves, and pumps, are from the commercial library TIL 3.11.0. The refrigerant library TIL-Media contains a variety of commonly used refrigerants, mixtures, and secondary fluids. DaVE, a data visualization software, was used to plot the log p-h, T-h diagrams for modeled bottom cycles created in MATLAB file (filename.mat) by Dymola simulation [33].

Several assumptions and simplifications have been made to create the models, they are therefore a simplified representation of reality. To simplify the models and set the thermodynamic properties within the components of TIL library following assumption were made:

1. There is zero pressure loss inside the components and piping network due to friction.
2. Heat losses to the ambient are neglected from the components.
3. Vapor and liquid phase are in thermodynamic equilibrium inside the liquid separator.
4. The heat exchangers have been dimensioned to cover the required load with a temperature pinch of maximum 5K.
5. Solution Pump efficiency is set to 100%.
6. Sea water to city cold water heat exchanger is assumed to have approach temperature of 2K and is not considered in the simulation model.
7. In the ACHP cycle the mixing point of vapor and IHEX outlet, the process of mixing is adiabatic.
8. In the ACHP model, Rich solution leaving the absorber outlet is saturated liquid.

The simulation of a Dymola model generally proceeds as follows. First, the state variables are initialized based on the initial equations and start values. Then, the continuous time integration starts and results are saved at the time intervals until completion. The selection of correct initial values is therefore key for simulation success. The initial state point calculation for each cycle was performed using Refprop [48]. Refprop is a database of fluid thermodynamic and transport properties developed by NIST. It covers data for a wide range of fluids and mixtures, especially those used in refrigeration and heat pump cycles. All models simulated for a time period of 3600 seconds or more, with one time interval per second. It was assumed that any errors due to incorrect initialization values would have stabilized after one hour of simulation.

5.5 Numerical

It is important to provide initial values for solving differential equations in dynamic systems used by Dymola. A baseline calculation of state points helps the dynamic solver to converge and provide accurate and stable simulations. For this purpose, an initial calculation for each state point was developed using Refprop. The calculation tables are provided in Appendix C.

5.6 General System Model in Dymola

5.6.1 R717 Cycle

The R717 cycle was modeled in a single model structure and can be found in its entirety in figure 5.13. The model has been divided into several submodels by segmenting the whole cycle into different parts with initial values and component sizing until a closed loop is formed to run the simulation. The model was set up based on component models of the two compressors, an evaporator, a desuperheater, two condenser, two expansion valves, an open-flash intercooler, a separator, three auxiliary pump and one sea water heat exchanger.

To extract heat from seawater at 15°C, a plate-type heat exchanger was used from the component library. The dimensions of all the heat exchangers are shown Appendix B. Since the pressure drop inside the components and piping is assumed to be zero in this work, the heat transfer coefficients of the heat exchangers were not assumed but rather calculated using different coefficients found in the literature. The theoretical background of these coefficients is discussed in Appendix A.

Figure 5.12: Log Ph diagram for R717 cycle

The temperature pinch of the evaporator and condensers were set at 5K. The seawater and domestic cold water are pumped at 4 bar. It was assumed that the evaporation temperature is 10°C for a 5K difference with the cold city water inlet. For a 70°C hot water outlet at the condenser, the condenser inlet temperature was set at 80°C. These set temperatures provide

evaporator and condenser working pressures, which were determined by Refprop to be 6.16 bar and 41.5 bar, respectively.

State Points	Process
1-2	Compression by LP compressor (6.16 bar to 15.6 bar)
2-3	Compressed vapor to open flash intercooler
3-4	Compression by HP compressor (15.6 bar to 41.5 bar)
4-5	Desuperheater heat recovery
5-6	Condensation of Ammonia and water heating
6-7	Expansion to open flash intercooler at intermediate pressure (15.6 bar)
8-7-3	Liquid and vapor phase separation for expansion and compression inlet
8-9	Expansion to liquid separator at low pressure (6.16 bar)
10-9-12-1	Evaporation at -10°C, phase separation, and compression inlet

Table 5.1: Processes in the R717 cycle based on Log P-h diagram

To achieve minimum compression work, a lower compression ratio (π) is required from a thermodynamic point of view (as previously discussed in section 3.3). The compression ratio and intermediate pressure for a two-stage solution can be determined by the following equation of pressure ratio.

The pressure ratio π is defined as:

$$\pi = \frac{P_H}{P_M} = \frac{P_M}{P_L} \quad (5.1)$$

and the intermediate pressure P_M is given by:

$$P_M = \sqrt{P_H \cdot P_L}$$

It is also important to note that an increased pressure ratio results in reduced isentropic efficiency of the compressors. Additionally, to avoid superheat loss, compression done in two stages has more advantages. As can be understood from the compression work of an ideal gas equation:

$$\dot{W} = \dot{m} \cdot R \cdot T_1 \left(\left(\pi^{\frac{k-1}{k}} \right) - 1 \right)$$

In addition to two-stage compression, the system was designed to have two-stage expansion.

Figure 5.13: Graphical representation of R717 heat pump model implemented with TIL library in Modelica/Dymola, Green line represents low pressure fluid line, violet represents intermediate pressure fluid, orange represents high pressure fluid line and blue represents auxiliary water line

From the low-pressure compressor, warm discharge gas will enter the intermediate pressure receiver or the open flash intercooler and be cooled down close to the intermediate saturation temperature, a process known as "bubble through" cooling arrangement. In the same open flash intercooler, the condensed high-pressure fluid is expanded into the open flash intercooler and subcooled. The vapor fraction after high-pressure fluid expansion and the cooled gas from the low-pressure compressor are compressed with another high-pressure compressor before being sent to the desuperheater and condenser for heat rejection.

5.6.2 R744 Cycle

The R744 cycle was also constructed (figure 5.15) in segmented submodels until the full cycle was completed for the refrigeration flow. In addition, component sizing and initialization were given to the individual components of the cycle to ensure accurate convergence of the integration. The model was set up based on component models of one compressor, an evaporator, a desuperheater, three gas coolers, a subcooler, one IHEX, one expansion valve, a separator, two auxiliary pumps, and one seawater heat exchanger. Similar to the R717 cycle, the evaporation temperature was set to 10°C, and the corresponding evaporator working pressure for liquid CO₂ was calculated from Refprop to be 45.015 bar.

Figure 5.14: Log Ph diagram for R744 cycle

A transcritical CO₂ cycle was chosen to take advantage of the temperature glide during heat rejection in the gas cooler. The state points at the gas cooler inlet for different gas cooler pressures were calculated to heat cold domestic water from 13°C to 70°C, with gas cooler pressures ranging from 75 bar to 110 bar. To achieve a sink outlet temperature of 70°C, an initial gas cooler pressure of 90 bar was selected for the model development. The change in gas cooler pressure will obviously impact the shaft power consumption by the compressor. A comparative study of changing gas cooler pressure and its influence on power consumption is outlined in the results section.

State Points	Process
1-2	Superheating by IHEX
2-3	Compressed by piston compressor (45.02 bar to 90 bar)
3-4	Gas cooler heat rejection to water
4-5	Heat rejection to IHEX
5-6	Subcooling by city cold water
6-7	Expansion of subcooled CO ₂ to evaporator (at 45.02 bar)
7-1	Evaporation in the heat exchanger

Table 5.2: Processes in the R717 cycle based on Log P-h diagram

The seawater rejects heat to cold city water, starting at 15°C and exiting with an outlet temperature of 10-11°C. The warm domestic water evaporates the CO₂ fluid in the evaporator at a constant evaporation temperature of 10°C. The log P-h diagram of the R744 cycle illustrates the cycle configuration for an evaporation pressure of 45 bar and a gas cooler pressure of 90 bar, as shown in Figure 5.14.

Two energy efficiency features for cycle performance improvement have been considered in this system: an IHEX and a subcooler configuration. The heat released from the subcooler warms the cold city water at the inlet of the evaporator. The subcooler is built as a pipe coiled around another pipe with heat resistance.

5.6.3 ACHP Cycle

The working principle of the ACHP system has already been covered in Section 3.6. For the simulation, a simplified sketch was used to inject a lean solution into the dry screw compressor to observe the compressor's outlet temperature and replicate the setup at the NTNU EPT lab. Unlike the test rig, the numerical model does not include a high-pressure liquid separator, as it is not essential to the absorption cycle. A schematic diagram of the model is shown in Figure 3.14.

To simulate the hybrid ammonia-water absorption cycle, a working pressure of 5 bar in the desorber and 30 bar in the absorber was set to run the system with lower pressure ratio and maintain higher isentropic efficiency of the screw compressor. Using a PTX diagram and placing the absorber and desorber on it (Figure 5.16), the inlet and outlet conditions of the absorber and desorber was determined from Refprop.

In Refprop, it is possible to define a mixture of ammonia and water and determine the thermodynamic properties at varying temperatures and pressures. For a predetermined desrober

Figure 5.15: Graphical representation of R744 heat pump model implemented with TIL library in Modelica/Dymola, Green line represents low pressure fluid line, orange represents high pressure fluid line, red line represents sub-cooling heat rejection, and blue represents auxiliary water line

pressure of 5 bar, the strong solution mass fraction was assumed 0.65 of Ammonia and a weak solution mass fraction of 0.32 ammonia. The following steps were sequential approach to obtain all the initial and set points for the model:

1. Set the target sink inlet temperature and target outlet temperature. By using the below formula, the heat load from the sink can be determined for any given mass flow rate.

$$Q_{\text{sink}} = \dot{m}_{\text{sink}} \cdot c_{p,\text{aux}} \cdot \Delta T_{\text{sink}} \quad (5.2)$$

2. Using the ammonia-water PTX diagram to decide the working pressure for the absorber (high pressure) and the desorber (low pressure), as illustrated in Figure 5.16.
3. The pinch point in all the heat exchangers was set to 5K. Therefore, with the determined pressure and corresponding temperature difference for a set concentration of rich solution,

Figure 5.16: Othmer diagram (PTX) of saturated liquid for an ammonia-water mixture with hybrid heat pump components. The blue line indicates ammonia vapor, the green line represents a strong ammonia-water mixture, and the orange line represents a lean ammonia-water mixture.

the inlet and outlet thermophysical properties can be calculated assuming the pinch difference ΔT_{pinch} from REFPROP. Also, the mass flow of rich solution can then be determined by using the following equation:

$$\dot{m}_{\text{rich}} = \frac{Q_{\text{sink}}}{h_{\text{absorber_inlet}} - h_{\text{absorber_outlet}}} \quad (5.3)$$

4. Decide the concentration of the lean solution and set the absorber outlet, solution pump inlet, and vapor concentration at the compressor inlet by using the PTX diagram. Corresponding thermophysical properties can again be calculated by REFPROP
5. The IHEX efficiency was set to 0.9, and the following energy balance equation helped to determine the unknown stream enthalpy for IHEX:

$$\varepsilon = \frac{h_{\text{IHEX_hot_stream_inlet}} - h_{\text{IHEX_hot_stream_outlet}}}{h_{\text{IHEX_cold_stream_outlet}} - h_{\text{IHEX_cold_stream_inlet}}} \quad (5.4)$$

6. The source inlet temperature and mass flow are also set, and the cooling load at the desorber can be calculated by the following equation:

Figure 5.17: Graphical representation of ACHP heat pump model implemented with TIL library in Modelica/Dymola, Green line represents vapor line, orange represents lean solution line, pink line represents rich solution line, blue represents auxiliary water line, red represents hot water line

$$Q_{\text{source}} = \dot{m}_{\text{source}} \cdot c_{p,\text{aux}} \cdot \Delta T_{\text{source}} \quad (5.5)$$

- It is possible to calculate the quality of the desorber outlet and the circulation ratio from that. REFPROP provides the quality of the mixture for the known state points like pressure, temperature, and composition, and the below formula was utilized to calculate the corresponding circulation ratio:

$$CR = 1 - q_{\text{separator}} \quad (5.6)$$

- The lean solution mass flow can be determined by the following formula [4], and the vapor mass flow at the compressor inlet will be the difference between the rich and lean solution mass flows:

$$CR = \frac{\dot{m}_{\text{lean}}}{\dot{m}_{\text{rich}}} \quad (5.7)$$

- Once the vapor mass flow at the compressor inlet is known, the displacement (V_d) of the

compressor can be calculated using the following equation:

$$V_d = \frac{\dot{m}}{\lambda_{eff} \cdot n \cdot \rho_{suction}} \quad (5.8)$$

where:

- \dot{m} is the vapor mass flow rate
- λ_{eff} is the volumetric efficiency of the compressor
- n is the rotational speed of the compressor
- $\rho_{suction}$ is the density of the vapor at the inlet of the compressor
- V_d is the displacement in cubic meters (m³)

10. Finally the COP of the cycle can be calculated using below formula:

$$\text{COP}_{\text{cycle}} = \frac{Q_{\text{sink}}}{W_{\text{comp}} + W_{\text{pump}}} \quad (5.9)$$

A state point calculation of the ACHP cycle determined with the help of the PTX diagram and Refprop has been presented in Appendix C Table C.3.

The Dymola model for the ACHP was built based on component models of two compressors, a desorber, an absorber, one IHX, one solution pump, one auxiliary pump, one expansion valve, and one separator tank.

5.7 Steam Generation Model

To simulate steam generation, pressurized hot water at 4 bar and 120°C from the sink outlet of the ACHP model is expanded into a flash tank at a lower pressure of 1 bar. This sudden pressure drop causes a portion of the water to flash into steam by lowering the boiling point. A compressor connected to the flash tank steam outlet, equipped with a variable displacement volume, further pressurizes and superheats the steam to meet the target heat load. In the proposed steam generation model, the compressor increases the steam pressure from 1 bar to 2 bar, achieving a temperature of 193°C superheated steam.

Figure 5.18: Dymola model for steam generation

Graphical representation of the model is illustrated in Figure 5.18. The key components used include a simple pump, an efficient compressor, a separator tank, and a volume component from the TIL library to ensure consistent mass flow to the compressor inlet.

6 Model Development in Dymola

This section explains the step-by-step development of the R717, R744 and ACHP model in Dymola. The components were added sequentially until a complete circuit was formed, creating a closed loop. The process starts with the evaporator or desorber, following the direction of the working fluid flow through the components until it re-enters the evaporator through the expansion valve.

The System Information Manager (SIM) is necessary in all system models of the TIL library. The SIM defines the substances used in the component models of the system. These substances are selected by replaceable records in the SIM model. The SIM model includes three replaceable records for each medium type: VLEFluids, Gases, and Liquids [78].

Model: TIL.SystemInformationManager

It is important to configure the media setting as ‘TIL.Utilities.MediaConfigurationForMixtures’ in each component of the model, since an ammonia-water mixture from the TIL media library is used as the mixed fluid for ACHP cycle.

6.1 Heat Exchanger

In the ACHP cycle, the absorber, IHEX, and desorber are modeled to replicate the geometry of the "Osenbrück 4.0 Heat Pump". In the R744 model, the evaporator, gas cooler, and IHEX are assumed to be brazed plate heat exchangers, similar to the "Osenbrück 4.0 Heat Pump". Similarly, the evaporator, condenser, and desuperheater in the R717 cycle are also defined as brazed plate heat exchangers.

Choosing a plate-type heat exchanger geometry simplifies the calculation of heat transfer coefficients for different streams due to the availability of data and correlations for this type of heat exchanger. All streams in the models follow a counter-current flow direction, enhancing heat transfer efficiency.

6.1.1 Plate Geometry

The geometric parameters of a Plate Heat Exchanger (PHE) are defined as follows (see Figure 6.1):

- Chevron Angle (β): Ranges from 22° to 65° , affecting thermal efficiency and pressure drop [13]. A lower angle indicates lower thermal efficiency and pressure drop, while a higher angle indicates higher thermal efficiency and pressure drop.
- Enlargement Factor (ϕ): The ratio of the developed length to the protracted length.
- Mean Flow Channel Gap (b): The actual gap available for flow, defined as $b = p - t$.
- Channel Flow Area (A_x): The actual flow area, defined as $A_x = bL_w$.
- Channel Equivalent Diameter (d_e): Defined as:

$$d_e = \frac{4A_x}{P} \quad \text{where} \quad P = 2(b + \phi L_w) = 2\phi L_w.$$

Since $b \ll L_w$:

$$d_e = \frac{2b}{\phi}.$$

In heat exchangers, the overall heat transfer coefficient can be calculated as follows:

$$U = \frac{\dot{Q}}{A_{ht} \cdot \text{LMTD}}$$

The Log Mean Temperature Difference (LMTD) is defined as:

$$\text{LMTD} = \frac{(T_{\text{hot,in}} - T_{\text{cold,out}}) - (T_{\text{hot,out}} - T_{\text{cold,in}})}{\ln \left(\frac{T_{\text{hot,in}} - T_{\text{cold,out}}}{T_{\text{hot,out}} - T_{\text{cold,in}}} \right)}$$

If the surface area of the heat exchanger is unknown, the U value can be determined by calculating the convective heat transfer coefficient of the hot and cold streams in a plate-type heat exchanger. This is done using correlations presented in table 6.1. For the ACHP cycle, the ammonia-water mixture side absorption and desorption heat transfer coefficient is estimated by the research work presented by Jensen [38]. Detailed theoretical background for the referred correlations used in the research work presented in Appendix A.

After determining the convective heat transfer coefficients and considering the known conductive heat resistance of the heat exchanger material, the overall heat transfer coefficient U can be

Figure 6.1: Sketch of Geometrical Features of the Heat Exchangers

calculated, and the required area for the plate heat exchanger can be finalized. The calculations use the following variables:

- α_{cold} : heat transfer coefficient of the cold stream [$\text{W}/(\text{m}^2 \cdot \text{K})$]
- α_{hot} : heat transfer coefficient of the hot stream [$\text{W}/(\text{m}^2 \cdot \text{K})$]
- t : thickness of the heat exchanger plate [m]
- k : thermal conductivity of the heat exchanger plate material [$\text{W}/(\text{m} \cdot \text{K})$]

Combining these terms, the overall heat transfer coefficient is:

$$\frac{1}{U} = \frac{1}{\alpha_{\text{cold}}} + \frac{1}{\alpha_{\text{hot}}} + \frac{t}{k} \quad (6.1)$$

Tables 6.3, 6.2, and 6.4 summarize the correlation values (α) used for the "ConstantAlpha" heat transfer model. These values apply to both the hot and cold streams in all heat exchangers utilized in the R717, R744, and ACHP cycles.

Component Name	System	Fluid	Correlation
Evaporator	CO ₂ bottom Cycle	CO ₂	Martin [53] , Ayub [13]
Evaporator	CO ₂ bottom Cycle	Water	Martin [53]
Gas cooler	CO ₂ bottom Cycle	CO ₂	Martin [53] , Kuo et al. [46]
Gas cooler	CO ₂ bottom Cycle	Water	Martin [53]
IHEX	CO ₂ bottom Cycle	CO ₂	Martin [53]
IHEX	CO ₂ bottom Cycle	CO ₂	Martin [53]
Evaporator	NH ₃ bottom cycle	NH ₃	Martin [53] , Ayub [13]
Evaporator	NH ₃ bottom cycle	Water	Martin [53] , Ayub [13]
Condenser	NH ₃ bottom cycle	NH ₃	Martin [53] , Kuo et al. [46]
Condenser	NH ₃ bottom cycle	Water	Martin
Desuperheater	NH ₃ bottom cycle	NH ₃	Martin [53] , Kuo et al. [46]
Desuperheater	NH ₃ bottom cycle	Water	Martin
Absorber	ACHP	NH ₃ -Water	Martin [53], Táboas et al. [77]
Absorber	ACHP	Water	Martin [53]
Desorber	ACHP	NH ₃ -Water	Martin [53], Bell [17]
Desorber	ACHP	Water	Martin [53]
IHEX	ACHP	NH ₃ -Water	Martin [53]
IHEX	ACHP	NH ₃ -Water	Martin [53]

Table 6.1: Correlations used for determining heat transfer coefficient

Variable	Model	Evaporator	Desuperheater	Condenser
VLE fluid	Heat Transfer Model	ConstantAlpha 7947 W/m ² K	ConstantAlpha 72478 W/m ² K	ConstantAlpha 19127 W/m ² K
	Pressuredropmodel	dp = 0 Pa	dp = 0 Pa	dp = 0 Pa
Liquid	Heat Transfer Model	ConstantAlpha 7152 W/m ² K	ConstantAlpha 3124.63 W/m ² K	ConstantAlpha 12725 W/m ² K
	Pressuredropmodel	dp = 0 Pa	dp = 0 Pa	dp = 0 Pa
Wall	Wall material	stainlessSteel	stainlessSteel	stainlessSteel
	Conduction model	Geometrybased conduction	Geometrybased conduction	Geometrybased conduction

Table 6.2: R717 Model: VLE Fluid, Liquid, and Wall Specifications

Variable	Model	Evaporator	Internal HEX	Gas Cooler
VLE fluid	Heat Transfer Model	ConstantAlpha 2046 W/m ² K	ConstantAlpha 8121.6 W/m ² K	ConstantAlpha 6594.57 W/m ² K
	Pressuredropmodel	dp = 0 Pa	dp = 0 Pa	dp = 0 Pa
Liquid	Heat Transfer Model	ConstantAlpha 7152 W/m ² K		ConstantAlpha 12725 W/m ² K
	Pressuredropmodel	dp = 0 Pa		dp = 0 Pa
VLE fluid	Heat Transfer Model		ConstantAlpha 6,035.57 W/m ² K	
	Pressuredropmodel		dp = 0 Pa	
Wall	Wall material	stainlessSteel	stainlessSteel	stainlessSteel
	Conduction model	Geometrybased conduction	Geometrybased conduction	Geometrybased conduction

Table 6.3: R744 Model: VLE Fluid, Liquid, and Wall Specifications

Variable	Model	Desorber	Internal HEX	Absorber
VLE fluid	Heat Transfer Model	ConstantAlpha 3200 W/m ² K	ConstantAlpha 4646 W/m ² K	ConstantAlpha 7000 W/m ² K
	Pressuredropmodel	dp = 0 Pa	dp = 0 Pa	dp = 0 Pa
Liquid	Heat Transfer Model	ConstantAlpha 10826 W/m ² K		ConstantAlpha 7519 W/m ² K
	Pressuredropmodel	dp = 0 Pa		dp = 0 Pa
VLE fluid	Heat Transfer Model		ConstantAlpha 3467 W/m ² K	
	Pressuredropmodel		dp = 0 Pa	
Wall	Wall material	stainlessSteel	stainlessSteel	stainlessSteel
	Conduction model	Geometrybased conduction	Geometrybased conduction	Geometrybased conduction

Table 6.4: ACHP Model: VLE Fluid, Liquid, and Wall Specifications

6.2 Compressor Models

Efficiency-type compressor models were selected from the TIL model library as `TIL.VLEFluidComponents.Compressors.EffCompressor` for all compressor in all three cycles. The input parameters of this component are: rotational speed (Hz), displacement (m^3), fixed volumetric, and isentropic efficiencies. The compressor efficiencies are assumed as no data are available for the actual functional unit. The displacement of the compressor was calculated using the following formula:

$$V_{\text{disp}} = \frac{\dot{m}}{\eta_{\text{vol}} \cdot n \cdot \rho_{\text{suction}}} \quad (6.2)$$

where η_{vol} is the volumetric efficiency, \dot{m} is the mass flow at the compressor inlet, ρ_{suction} is the density of the suction gas, and n is the speed.

Figure 6.2: ACHP Cycle: Two stage compression for lean solution injection. Snippet from Dymola

It was not possible to inject the lean solution directly into the compressor for the ACHP cycle. Therefore, a two-stage compressor system was introduced, as presented in Figure 6.2. Since both the R717 and ACHP cycles were modeled with two compressors, the inlet gas pressure of the low-pressure compressor was set by assuming the vapor quality to be 1 at the outlet from the liquid separator. The inlet vapor pressure of the high-pressure compressor was set

using Equation 5.1. For the R744 cycle, the inlet gas pressure of the compressor was also set by assuming the vapor quality to be 1.

Variable	Compressor LP	Compressor HP
Compressor type	effCompressor	effCompressor
use mechanical port	TRUE	TRUE
displacement [m ³] (70 °C supply temp.)	$2.166\,543 \times 10^{-3}$	$1.818\,415 \times 10^{-3}$
Volumetric efficiency	0.8	0.8
Isentropic efficiency	0.7	0.7

Table 6.5: R717- Compressor Specifications for Dymola

Variable	Compressor LP	Compressor HP
Compressor type	effCompressor	effCompressor
use mechanical port	TRUE	TRUE
displacement [m ³] (120 °C supply temp.)	1.293×10^{-3}	4.447×10^{-4}
Volumetric efficiency	0.8	0.8
Isentropic efficiency	0.7	0.7

Table 6.6: ACHP- Compressor Specifications for Dymola

Variable	Compressor-single stage
Compressor type	effCompressor
use mechanical port	TRUE
displacement [m ³] (70°C supply temp.)	2.05×10^{-4}
Volumetric efficiency	0.8
Isentropic efficiency	0.7

Table 6.7: R744- Compressor Specifications for Dymola

6.3 Other Components

6.3.1 Separator Tanks

The separator and open flash intercooler were modeled using the separator component `TIL.VLEFluidComponents.Separators.Separator` from the component library. To ensure mass balance for the evaporator and the separator tank, an additional pump component was included in the R717 system. In the real system, the mass flow from the separator to the evaporator is assumed to be purely based on gravitational forces. The influence of pipes when modeling the heat pump systems was avoided to simplify the simulation.

6.3.2 Solution Pump

The solution pump of the ACHP model was selected from the following component in the TIL library. The mass flow of the lean solution was set fixed for varying operating conditions based on the circulation ratio.

Model: `TIL.VLEFluidComponents.Pumps.SimplePump`

Simple pump model

Preset variable: m_{flow}

Variable	Tube A, CO ₂	Tube B, Water
Tube length	10 m	10 m
Inner diameter	-	18 mm
Tube side heat transfer model	Gungor Winterton '87	Gnielinski Dittus Boelter
Enable heat ports	TRUE	TRUE
Pressure drop model	dp = 0 Pa	dp = 0 Pa
Wall heat conduction model	Geometry based	Geometry based
Wall material	Stainless Steel	Stainless Steel

Table 6.8: Subcooler specification in Dymola

6.3.3 Subcooler in R744 Model

The subcooler is built as a pipe coiled around another pipe, which is modeled as two tubes with a heat resistance. The high-pressure liquid outlet from the IHX releases heat to the cold city water inlet on the evaporator side of the R744 model, as shown in Figure 5.15. The heat resistance was modeled by enabling heat ports on each tube and setting the heat resistance at each port.

6.4 Controller Design

6.4.1 Mass Flow rate

Two cases have been established to run the heat pump system: one for a fixed load and another for a variable load. The fixed load corresponds to the highest thermal demand from the condenser, absorber, or gas cooler. The variable load follows the thermal demand profile presented in Figure 5.12.

Figure 6.3: Supply temperature control for R717 cycle by HP compressor, snippet from Dynola

For the bottom cycles, at a supply temperature of 70°C and a heat load of 610 kW, the mass flow of 13°C cold city water in the condenser or gas cooler is set to 2.61 kg/s. For a heat load of 478 kW, the mass flow is set to 1.99 kg/s, and for a 30 kW heat load, it is set to 0.125 kg/s. For operating conditions with supply temperatures of 75°C, 80°C, 85°C, and 90°C, the mass flow rate varies based on the following formula:

$$Q = \dot{m} \cdot C_p \cdot \Delta T \quad (6.3)$$

Since the top cycle (ACHP) has supply inlets for the sink and source from the bottom cycle, the source inlet mass flow is set to a fixed 1.2 kg/s, while the sink inlet varies between 1 kg/s and 0.5 kg/s.

For a fixed mass flow rate, `use_massFlowRateInput` is set to true for boundary and simple pumps. For varied mass flow input, `Modelica.Blocks.Sources.CombiTimeTable` is used for 0 to 3600 seconds with varied mass flow.

6.4.2 Compressor Speed

For varied supply temperature, the compressor speed is adjusted using a rotational boundary and a PI controller. The outlet temperature of the condenser, gas cooler, or absorber serves as the output parameter. The HP compressor speed is varied to supply the required mass flow of the working fluid to reject heat at these components at the set pressure (figure 6.3). To control the intermediate pressure, the low-pressure compressor speed is regulated with another PI controller for the R717 and ACHP models.

Figure 6.4: Desuperheater Controller snippet from Dymola

6.4.3 Controlling Orifice Valves

The high pressure of the compressor discharge for all three models is maintained by controlling the mass flow of the expansion valve. For the ACHP model, the injection mass flow of the lean

solution is controlled by another expansion valve with the help of a PI controller connected to it, regulating the effective flow area input. The mass flow is regulated to ensure the compressor discharge temperature is below 180°C.

6.4.4 Desuperheater of R717 Cycle

The mass flow of cold city water at the desuperheater inlet is controlled by adding another PI controller with a simple pump by sensing the quality at the desuperheater outlet. The quality of the desuperheater outlet is set to 1 to ensure the superheated vapor has rejected the maximum possible heat to cold city water before entering the condenser (figure 6.4).

6.5 Validation of Dymola Models

Two bottom cycle alternatives have been simulated to meet a fixed heating demand with varying sink outlet temperatures of 70, 75, 80, 85, and 90°C for hot water. Additionally, a variable heating demand profile was considered, and the model was subdivided based on these varying heating demands over a 24-hour period, covering the same range of temperatures. The 24-hour demand curve was sampled for 3600 seconds.

It was not possible to determine all parameter values using the components in the TIL library, particularly the isentropic and volumetric efficiencies of the compressors for the bottom cycle alternatives (R717 and R744).

Validation involves comparing the model's outcomes with corresponding experimental data. For validating the ACHP model, experimental data from an identical configuration was selected. The discrepancies between the model and the experimental data were quantified using the normalized root mean square deviation (NRMSD), defined as follows [54]:

$$\text{NRMSD} = \sqrt{\frac{\sum_t (y_{\text{sim}}(t) - y_{\text{exp}}(t))^2}{N_t}} / \sqrt{\frac{\sum_t (y_{\text{exp}}(t))^2}{N_t}} \quad (6.4)$$

Here, $y_{\text{sim}}(t)$ refers to the simulated value at time t , $y_{\text{exp}}(t)$ is the measured value at time t , and N_t is the number of time steps.

Since the experimental data and this project's thermal demand are not similar, the individual models were further validated using one steady-state scenario. Each model was modified with initial values, geometry, controlling parameters, etc., component by component, and as a system until performing adequately. Once all components produced the expected output (i.e., heat load, supply temperature, pressure control), the components were connected for a closed-loop simulation and rerun for a steady-state situation. This loop continued until the best steady-state outcome was observed from each simulation of the model.

6.6 Economic Evaluation

This section presents a comprehensive economic analysis comparing the investment in a new cascaded heat pump to the continuation of using an existing boiler. For the heat pump investment to be considered viable, it must be economically competitive with the traditional boiler [39].

The primary cost components for a hot water and steam generation system include the compressor, heat exchanger (HEX), and pump. The purchase equipment costs (PEC) are correlated as follows [60]:

Compressor:	Depends on type and swept volume
Pump:	Depends on drive
HEX:	Function of area and pressure limit
Motor:	Dependent on shaft power
Liquid Receiver:	Depends on volume and pressure limit

The purchased equipment costs for all major heat pump components were based on Danish intermediate trade business prices (TRB) and manufacturers' suggested retail prices (MRP) as reported in Ommen et al. [60]. The cost function can be expressed as:

$$PEC_y = PEC_w \left(\frac{X_y}{X_w} \right)^\alpha \quad (6.5)$$

Here, PEC_y represents the PEC for a component with capacity X_y , and PEC_w is the PEC at a base capacity X_w , as proposed in Ommen et al. [60]. For components in steam generation unit like compressor, flash tank, pump were assumed multiplication of 150 Euro to the 15% of the heating capacity of the cascade unit [15].

For some components, due to non-disclosure agreements, costs were estimated using the most similar available component data from the study.

The Total Capital Investment (TCI) can be calculated using the following equation, with a multiplication factor of 4.16 to account for additional costs such as installation, piping, instrumentation, electrical equipment, engineering and supervision, startup, and working capital:

$$TCI_{HTHP} = \sum_{i=1}^n PEC_{\text{component}} \cdot 4.16 \quad (6.6)$$

The capital recovery factor (CRF), which is a function of the effective interest rate, can be determined using the following equations :

$$CRF = \frac{i^{\text{eff}}(1 + i^{\text{eff}})^n}{(1 + i^{\text{eff}})^n - 1} \quad (6.7)$$

$$i^{\text{eff}} = \left(\frac{1 + i}{1 - i_L} \right) - 1 \quad (6.8)$$

where i is the interest rate, i_L is the inflation rate, and n is the project's technical lifetime.

To calculate the annual fuel cost for the heat pump and a steam boiler fueled by natural gas, the following equations are used :

$$FC_{HTHP} = \frac{Q \cdot C_{\text{el}} \cdot H}{COP} \quad (6.9)$$

$$FC_{\text{Boiler}} = \frac{Q \cdot C_{\text{NG}} \cdot H}{\eta_{\text{boiler}}} \quad (6.10)$$

Here, Q is the desired heat output, C_{el} and C_{NG} are the costs of electricity and natural gas per kWh, respectively. H represents the operating hours, COP is the Coefficient of Performance for the heat pump, and η_{boiler} is the efficiency of the steam boiler.

The present value of all expenses associated with each alternative project can be calculated using the following equation:

$$PV_j = TCI_j + \frac{FC_j}{CRF} + OMC_j \quad (6.11)$$

where OMC_j is the operation and maintenance cost for system j , excluding fuel costs and assumed to be a fixed percentage (20%) of TCI_j , the total capital investment for system j . For the natural gas boiler, capital investment costs are considered sunk costs, making maintenance costs negligible .

The net present value (NPV) is used to determine the viability of the heat pump investment and is calculated as follows. If the NPV is positive, the proposed steam generation heat pump

will be a cost-effective alternative to the existing steam boiler :

$$NPV_{HTHP} = PV_{Boiler} - PV_{HTHP} \quad (6.12)$$

The payback period (PBP), which indicates the time required to fully recover the total capital investment through reduced fuel and maintenance costs compared to the existing solution, is calculated using the following formula :

$$PBP_{HTHP} = \frac{TCI_{HTHP}}{(FC_{Boiler} - FC_{HTHP}) + (OMC_{Boiler} - OMC_{HTHP}) \cdot CRF} \quad (6.13)$$

7 Result

This chapter presents the most significant findings from the development of the cascaded heat pump model. The cascaded heat pump is divided into two cycles: the bottom cycle and the top cycle. This segmentation allows for a comparative analysis of the alternatives. The results aim to identify the optimal combinations of operating conditions for both cycles, which will provide a measurable payback period for the technological infrastructure investment.

Given the extensive number of models and results, the presentation structure is as follows: First, the results from the Dymola simulation of the individual cycles are presented. For each cycle, a set of predetermined simulation configurations was used to identify the best operating conditions and performance for a specified heat load. Next, the simulation results for the selected models under a varied load profile are discussed. Finally, the combined performance of the top and bottom cycles, under optimal conditions, is compared in terms of both technical and economic advantages.

7.1 Simulation Results: R717 Bottom cycle

For the R717 cycle, the following simulation configurations were established (see Table 7.1). These configurations are based on the target supply temperature at the condenser hot water outlet and the variation of the corresponding condenser working pressure required to achieve the target temperature. Initially, the set configurations were simulated for a fixed load demand by varying the cold city water mass flow at the condenser inlet.

System	Configuration	Supply temperature [C]	Condenser Pressure [bar]	Heat load [KW]
R717- Bottom cycle	A1	70	33.89	610
	A2	75	37.927	610
	A3	80	41.4	610
	A4	85	47	610
	A5	90	52	610

Table 7.1: Simulation configurations for R717- Bottom cycle

Table C.1 in Appendix C shows the initial thermodynamic values from Refprop for the A1 configuration, which formed the basis for creating a dynamic heat pump model in Dymola. These cycle points were used as initial values for the dynamic simulation model.

The Log P-H diagram created in Dymola from the simulation results of all five configurations for the R717 cycle (Figure 7.1) provides a visual representation of the pressure-enthalpy relationship across different configurations. Each cycle, from A1 to A5, is plotted to show the behavior of the working fluid as it undergoes phase changes and pressure variations within the system.

At a supply temperature of 70°C and a condenser pressure of 33.89 bar, the cycle demonstrates stable performance, with the refrigerant following a typical two-stage inter-cooler refrigeration cycle path. The superheat energy recovery from the desuperheater saturates the superheated vapor before it enters the condenser inlet. The enthalpy changes are significant at the evaporator and condenser stages, indicating effective heat absorption and rejection.

Figure 7.1: R717: Log P-H from Dymola simulation

Increasing the supply temperature to 75°C and the condenser pressure to 37.927 bar, the cycle shows higher pressure and enthalpy at the condenser outlet. At 80°C and a condenser pressure of 41.4 bar, the pressure-enthalpy curve shifts further upward, indicating a higher energy transfer consistent with the increased thermal demand.

With a supply temperature of 85°C and a condenser pressure of 47 bar, the system operates at significantly higher pressures. The enthalpy changes continue to follow the expected trend, showing greater energy absorption and rejection as the operational temperatures rise. At the highest tested supply temperature of 90°C and a condenser pressure of 52 bar, the cycle shows the highest pressures and enthalpies. This configuration pushes the system to its upper operational limits, demonstrating the maximum capacity of the R717 cycle to handle high thermal loads.

As the pressure ratio increases for cycle configurations A2, A3, A4, and A5, higher condensation temperatures are achieved, leading to higher supply temperatures for the hot water. Conversely, the latent heat of vaporization decreases as the saturation dome narrows at higher pressures.

Figure 7.2: R717- Time series vs Supply temperature and Heat load

This reduction in the latent heat of vaporization means that the refrigerant requires less energy to transition from the liquid phase to the vapor phase, thus requires reduced refrigerant charge.

Figure 7.3: R717- Time series vs HP compressor mass flow

The simulation results for the R717 heat pump system, depicted in plot 7.2, include five configurations (A1 to A5) with supply temperatures ranging from 70 °C to 90 °C and the heat load at the condenser. Since the mass flow of the 13 °C cold domestic water was varied to achieve a fixed output of 610 kW (as previously stated in section 6.4.1), configurations A1, A2, A3, A4, and A5 showed steady-state performance after 200 seconds while achieving the target supply temperature at the condenser outlet, as shown in the Supply Temperature vs. Time series plot on the same plot. For the A1 configuration, the heat load exceeded the target value of 610 kW,

which may be due to higher compressor mass flow from the high-pressure stage of the cycle compared to other configurations, as shown in figure 7.3.

7.1.1 R717-Steady state results from Dymola simulation

Table 7.2 presents the most important results from the steady-state conditions for all five models simulated in Dymola. The evaporator working pressure remained nearly constant due to the constant cooling load across all five cases. However, the intermediate pressure and condenser pressure varied as previously discussed.

Parameter	A1	A2	A3	A4	A5	Unit
COP Heating	3.50	3.28	2.97	2.78	2.717	[-]
HP Comp. Speed	33.97	31.34	33.27	31.50	30.06	[Hz]
LP Comp. Speed	59.16	57.87	58.07	60.52	58.65	[Hz]
HP Comp. mass flow	0.53	0.52	0.56	0.55	0.53	[kg/s]
LP Comp. mass flow	0.49	0.48	0.48	0.50	0.48	[kg/s]
Condenser Pressure	34.12	38.04	41.93	47.06	52.04	[bar]
Intermediate Pressure	14.46	15.29	15.98	17.02	17.91	[bar]
Low stage pressure	6.02	6.02	6.02	6.01	6.02	[bar]
HP Comp. discharge temp.	120.40	128.30	135.89	144.24	151.95	[°C]
LP Comp. discharge temp.	91.22	96.92	101.50	108.25	113.55	[°C]
HP Comp. Shaft work	92.55	96.33	110.59	113.74	116.91	[kW]
LP Comp. Shaft work	85.25	89.25	94.23	105.34	107.67	[kW]
Delivered Heating	623.97	609.57	609.64	609.84	610.02	[kW]
Desuperheater heat load	95.77	102.07	119.45	149.77	134.56	[kW]
Delivered Cooling	104.74	104.05	104.04	105.07	104.10	[kW]
Sink Outlet	70.00	75.00	79.99	85.00	90.00	[°C]
Desuperheater Outlet	120.16	128.03	135.57	143.26	151.54	[°C]
Source Outlet	11.34	11.35	11.35	11.34	11.35	[°C]
Sink Massflow	2.62	2.35	2.18	2.02	1.89	[kg/s]
Desuperheater Massflow	0.21	0.21	0.23	0.27	0.23	[kg/s]

Table 7.2: Results from steady state simulation of R717 model

The discharge temperature of the heat pump compressor increased with higher condenser pressures, which were set for higher supply temperatures. The desuperheater heat recovery achieved a maximum of 149.77 kW at a supply temperature of 85°C and a condenser pressure of 47.06 bar, which is the highest among all the models. This is because at 85°C, the water supply pump delivered the highest mass flow of water, hence the heat rejection increased.

Cold city water for all desuperheaters was maintained at a pressurized state of 4 bar. At this pressure, and with the heated water at the desuperheater outlet, the water was "subcooled," as verified by the thermal properties from Refprop.

Figure 7.4: R717 steady state: shaft-work and COP against supply temperature

Figure 7.4 shows the relationship between the condensing temperature and the work done by each compressor. It is evident that as the condensing temperature increases, the work done by each compressor also increases. Consequently, the COP of the system decreases for a fixed heat load. This relationship aligns with the COP formula, where an increase in temperature lift (ΔT) results in higher work required by the compressor.

Among the five simulated models, Model "A1" demonstrated the highest COP of 3.5 at a condenser pressure of 34.12 bar.

7.1.2 R717 Demand Profile

Since Model A1 shows the highest performance compared to other configurations, a thermal demand profile simulation for variation in supply temperature and mass flow was performed in Dymola.

Based on the thermal demand profile depicted in Figure 5.11, the system performance under varied load conditions was observed to assess its effectiveness in coping with load variations and ease of operation. As shown in Figure 7.5 (a) the heat load profile over time, with the simulated heat load (solid orange line) and the projected heat load (dashed purple line) of 610 KW. The heat load increases sharply at the beginning from 30KW to 595KW, stabilizes, and then shows a step change, indicating changes in the system's operating conditions due to the variation in the cold city water mass flow rate.

Figure 7.5: R717 simulation: Heat load and shaft work profile for variable sink mass flow at 70°C outlet

Figure 7.5 (b) presents the heat load at the condenser (blue line) and the total shaft work of the compressor (orange line). Initially, both the heat load and shaft work increase sharply, then stabilize, and exhibit step changes corresponding to heat rejection at the condenser. The smooth operation observed during the one-hour simulation indicates the robustness and effectiveness of Model A1 in handling load variations.

7.2 Simulation Results: R744 Bottom cycle

For the R744 cycle, the following (Table 7.3) simulation configurations were established to determine the best performance and compare the steady-state parameters. These configurations are based on the target supply temperature at the gas cooler hot water outlet and the variation of gas cooler pressure to achieve the target temperature. Initially, the set configurations were simulated for a fixed load demand by varying the cold city water mass flow rate.

System	Configuration	Supply temperature [°C]	Gas cooler Pressure [bar]	Heat load [KW]
R744 Bottom cycle	B1	70	90	610
	B2	75	95	610
	B3	80	100	610
	B4	85	105	610
	B5	90	110	610

Table 7.3: Simulation configurations for R744 Bottom cycle

Table C.2 in Appendix C shows the initial thermodynamic state points from Refprop for Model B1. These state points were used as initial values for the dynamic simulation model. For other system configurations (B2, B3, B4, and B5), the same state points were used except for the gas cooler pressure initialization, which was changed and controlled by varying the speed of the compressor.

Figure 7.6: Log P-h diagram for R744 model for predefined set configurations

The log P-H diagram (Figure 8.2) was plotted in DAVE by integrating simulation results of the five configurations. The plot shows that each cycle mimics a typical CO₂ transcritical cycle log P-H diagram and illustrates the phase changes occurring at the evaporator, as well as the

phase changes due to expansion after subcooling of supercritical CO₂. However, the COP of these cycle configurations will be less due to bad temperature fit between the CO₂ and the cold city water inlet.

Figure 7.7: R744 Simulation: Time plot of gas cooler pressure and supply temperature

Figure 7.7 (a) shows the steady-state simulation of varying gas cooler configurations for supply temperatures of 70, 75, 80, 85, and 90 °C. All configurations reached steady-state within 100 seconds, with higher supply temperatures resulting in higher steady-state pressures. This is due to the increased vapor pressure at higher temperatures.

Figure 7.7 (b) illustrates that the supply temperature also stabilized within 100 seconds for all configurations over a 3600-second run time. Initial temperature overshoots were more significant at higher supply temperatures, but all configurations settled to their respective steady-state values. The rapid stabilization in both pressure and temperature indicates that the gas cooler system is responsive and capable of maintaining desired conditions under varying operational parameters.

7.2.1 R744-Steady state results from Dymola simulation

Table 7.4 presents the most important results from the steady-state conditions for all five models simulated in Dymola. The evaporation temperature was set to 10°C for all five cases. The heat rejection from the gas cooler showed the highest 624 KW for configuration B1, constant 609 KW for all other configurations.

Parameter	B1	B2	B3	B4	B5	Unit
Refrigerant mass flow	3.57	3.29	3.17	3.08	3.03	[kg/s]
Gas cooler pressure	90.00	95.00	100.00	105.00	110.00	[bar]
Low Pressure	33.17	33.47	33.57	33.73	33.91	[bar]
Comp. discharge temp.	96.26	102.13	107.82	113.09	118.04	[°C]
Heat Load	624.00	609.59	609.72	609.88	610.06	[KW]
Sink outlet	70.00	75.00	80.00	85.00	90.00	[°C]
Gas cooler outlet	39.03	40.41	41.65	42.94	44.34	[°C]
Subcooler outlet	37.49	38.01	38.52	39.18	40.04	[°C]
Cooling Load	412.50	403.50	400.43	395.96	390.57	[KW]
Sink mass flow	2.62	2.35	2.18	2.02	1.89	[kg/s]
Shaft power	222.45	217.28	220.71	225.63	231.58	[KW]
COP	2.81	2.81	2.76	2.70	2.63	[-]

Table 7.4: R744 model: Steady state result from simulation

Figure 7.8 further illustrates the relationship between different simulation configurations. In Figure 7.8 -(a), the shaft power varies slightly across configurations, with configuration B1 requiring the most power at 222.45 kW, and configuration B5 requiring the least power at 231.58 kW. The Coefficient of Performance (COP) decreases marginally from 2.81 in B1 to 2.63 in B5, which is a decrease of approximately 6.4%.

In Figure 7.8-(b), the heat load remains nearly constant across all configurations, around 609 kW. The refrigerant mass flow decreases significantly from 3.57 kg/s in B1 to 3.08 kg/s in B5, a reduction of about 13.7%. indicating that less refrigerant is required as the pressure increases across configurations for a fixed gas cooler heat load.

Figure 7.8: R744: Configurations performance for different supply temperatures

7.2.2 Optimum gas cooler pressure

Since configuration B1 shows better performance, another set of model configurations was developed to determine the optimum gas cooler pressure at 70°C. Table 7.5 shows the model configurations developed with the boundary conditions.

System	Configuration	Supply temperature [°C]	Gas cooler Pressure [bar]	Heat load [KW]
R744 Bottom cycle	B1-90	70	90	624
	B1-95	70	95	624
	B1-100	70	100	624
	B1-105	70	105	624
	B1-110	70	110	624
	B1-115	70	115	624
	B1-120	70	120	624

Table 7.5: Simulation configurations for optimum gas cooler pressure

Figure 7.9 shows the performance metrics for the R744 system across different gas cooler pressures at a fixed supply temperature of 70°C. The configurations range from B1-90 to B1-120, with gas cooler pressures from 90 bar to 120 bar, respectively. Figure 7.9 (a) depicts the relationship between shaft power and COP (Coefficient of Performance) for different gas cooler pressures.

Figure 7.9: R744: Optimum gas cooler pressure

The shaft power decreases as the gas cooler pressure increases from 90 bar to 120 bar. Specifically, it drops from 222.45 kW at 90 bar to 180.48 kW at 110 bar, a reduction of approximately 18.9%. This indicates that higher gas cooler pressures result in lower energy consumption by the system.

Figure 7.10: R744: Log P-H for varied gas cooler pressure at fixed supply temperature

The COP increases as the gas cooler pressure increases up to 110 bar, where it peaks at 3.46. Beyond 110 bar, the COP slightly decreases. For instance, the COP at 90 bar is 2.81, which increases to 3.46 at 110 bar and then slightly drops to 3.41 at 120 bar. This shows that there is an optimal gas cooler pressure (around 110 bar) that maximizes the system's efficiency. Figure

7.9 (b) illustrates the gas cooler outlet temperature and gas cooler pressure across different configurations.

The gas cooler outlet temperature decreases significantly with increasing gas cooler pressure. For example, it decreases from 37.49°C at 90 bar to 15.13°C at 120 bar, a reduction of approximately 59.6%. This reduction in outlet temperature indicates improved heat rejection as the pressure increases. Steady-state results for these configurations to determine the optimum gas cooler pressure are presented in Table B.4 in Appendix B.

Figure 7.10 illustrates the closed cycles for optimum gas cooler configurations in a log P-h diagram. As can be seen, as the gas cooler pressure increases, the gas cooler outlet temperature of CO₂ and the subcooled CO₂ temperature decrease. Additionally, the cooling load increases for higher gas cooler pressures. It is also evident from the plot that higher pressures result in larger enthalpy drops during expansion.

7.2.3 R744 Demand Profile

Since B1-110 demonstrates optimal gas cooler performance with the lowest compressor shaft work and superior cooling load for a fixed heat demand, a thermal demand profile simulation was conducted in Dymola to examine the variation in mass flow for a fixed supply temperature.

Figure 7.11: R744: Heat load profile at gas cooler for varied sink mass flow

The heat load profile over time is depicted in Figure 7.11(a) with the simulated heat load (solid red line) and the projected heat load (dashed purple line). Initially, the heat load remains relatively low and stable at around 30 KW, corresponding to a water mass flow rate of 0.125 kg/s at the gas cooler inlet. Around 1050 seconds, the projected demand sharply increases to 624 KW as plant operation starts, thereby escalating the thermal demand for the process. The simulated heat load does not change abruptly but rather follows a curved trajectory in response

to the step increase in the demand profile.

The shaft work of the compressor, as shown in Figure 7.11 (b), indicates that the system requires some time to adjust to the sharp increase in heat load demand. At approximately 2250 seconds, the heat load decreases to around 476 KW, with a corresponding water mass flow rate at the sink of 1.99 kg/s. The model responds gradually to this change, and the rejected heat load at the gas cooler slightly exceeds the projected heat demand. Around 2800 seconds, the plant ceases its cleaning operation, resulting in a thermal demand reduction to 30 KW at 70°C for the utility demand of the premises. The simulation exhibits a smooth transition profile for this step-down in demand, as illustrated in the figure.

The smooth operation observed during the simulation underscores the robustness and effectiveness of the R744 model in managing load variations. The system demonstrates a rapid response to changes in thermal demand, stabilizes its operation efficiently, and maintains consistent performance throughout the simulation period. This indicates that the model is well-suited for handling dynamic thermal loads and can effectively manage operational transitions.

7.3 Simulation: ACHP Model

For the top cycle of the cascaded heat pump, the ACHP system was modeled with different sink and source inlet temperatures, which are fed either from the R744 cycle or the R717 bottom cycle in the cascaded system. The ACHP cycle is assumed to produce pressurized hot water, which is then used to generate steam in combination with a flash tank system. The configurations and results of the ACHP cycle are discussed in this section. An overview of steam generation by the flash tank and the effect of the compressor on overall performance are also discussed later in Section 7.4.

Firstly, the results obtained from sink/source inlet temperatures of 70/70, 75/75, 80/80, 85/85, and 90/90 °C for a sink outlet temperature of 120 °C, with a fixed source and sink mass flow rate of 1 and 1.2 kg/s, absorption and desorption pressure of 30 bar and 5 bar respectively, are presented here to understand the transition due to key parameter changes. Later, steady-state results obtained from the simulation are presented to identify the best boundary configuration.

Figure 7.12: Variation of of lean solution mass flow and its impact of (a) shaft work (b) Circulation ratio

Figure 7.12 presents two plots illustrating the variation of lean solution mass flow rate and its impact on shaft power and circulation ratio. In Figure 7.12(a), the relationship between the lean solution mass flow rate and shaft power is shown. The plot indicates that, in general, the shaft power increases as the lean solution mass flow rate rises. However, an interesting deviation occurs at mass flow rates below approximately 0.178 kg/s. In this range, the shaft power increases even as the lean solution mass flow rate decreases. Figure 7.12(b) depicts the correlation between lean solution mass flow rate and circulation ratio. This plot demonstrates

a consistent trend where the circulation ratio increases steadily with the lean solution mass flow rate. The relationship appears linear, indicating a direct proportionality between the two variables.

Figure 7.13: Variation of of rich solution mass fraction and its relation to (a) COP (b) Circulation ratio

Figure 7.13 presents two plots that illustrate the impact of rich solution concentration on the coefficient of performance (COP) and circulation ratio. In Figure 7.13(a), the relationship between the rich solution concentration (X_{rich}) and COP is observed. The COP begins to decline steadily as X_{rich} continues to increase. This trend indicates that higher concentrations of the ammonia solution negatively impact the system's overall efficiency. The decline in COP becomes more pronounced as X_{rich} exceeds 0.70, where the performance drops significantly with further increases in rich solution concentration. In contrast, Figure 7.13(b) shows the correlation between X_{rich} and the circulation ratio. Here, with the increase of the circulation ratio X_{rich} rises.

7.3.1 Steady state results from Dymola simulation

The configurations of the ACHP cycles simulated in Dymola are further illustrated in Table 7.6. Furthermore, table 7.7 presents the most important results from the steady-state conditions for all given configurations presented in Table 7.6. For the ACHP cycle, the load variation profile was not analyzed.

The high pressure (HP) remains constant at 30 bar across all conditions, indicating that the system maintains a steady pressure level in the absorber, absorbing ammonia vapor by the lean ammonia solution at a fixed pressure and producing heat through the absorption process. The low pressure (LP) is constant at 5 bar, ensuring effective operation of the desorber where the

source water releases heat to the rich ammonia solution at a fixed desorber pressure. As the source glide reduces, the cooling load decreases at the desorber. All five configurations were able to maintain an intermediate pressure of 12.25 bar under the boundary condition of producing 210 KW of heat load. To match the heat load at the absorber, the sink mass flow was controlled, ranging from 1 kg/s to 1.667 kg/s for sink inlet temperatures of 70°C and 90°C respectively.

With the increase of ΔT_{lift} , the lean solution mass flow decreased, as can be seen from Figure 7.14(a). The relationship is linear for a fixed sink outlet temperature of 120°C and 210 KW of heat load. Lorenz efficiency is an important factor to evaluate system performance in mixed refrigerant systems. Another plot in Figure 7.14(b) shows the relationship between Lorenz efficiency and temperature lift. The Lorenz efficiency is plotted as a function of the mean temperature lift at constant heat sink and heat source temperatures. As the temperature lift increases between the heat source and heat sink, the Lorenz efficiency increases linearly.

Configuration	Sink/Source Inlet [°C]	Sink outlet [°C]	Heat Load [KW]	Sink Mass flow [Kg/s]	Source Mass flow [Kg/s]
C1	70/70	120	210	1	1.2
C2	75/75	120	210	1	1.2
C3	80/80	120	210	1	1.2
C4	85/85	120	210	1	1.2
C5	90/90	120	210	1	1.2

Table 7.6: Simulation configurations for ACHP- Top cycle

Figure 7.14: Delt T lift and its relation with (a) lean solution mass flow (b) eta lorentz

Among all cycle configurations, configuration C1 has the highest COP of 3.55 and the lowest power consumption by compressor shafts, though the pump work was highest for this

Figure 7.15: ACHP models steady state performance (a) Work vs COP (b) Heat load vs Sink outlet Temperature

configuration for a sink inlet temperature of 70°C , as can be seen from Figure 7.15(a). As the source inlet temperature increases from 70°C to 90°C , the lean solution mass fraction also decreases gradually, which results in a decrease in pump work with an increase in source inlet temperature. Configuration C5 showed a sink outlet temperature of 118°C and a heat load of 203.59 KW, as illustrated in Figure 7.15(b). This configuration maintained a consistent heat load while adjusting the sink outlet temperature to optimize performance.

Configuration	C1	C2	C3	C4	C5	Unit
Source outlet Temp.	39.80	45.81	51.72	57.62	63.61	[C]
HP	30.00	30.00	30.00	30.00	30.00	[bar]
Sink outlet Temp.	120.00	120.00	120.00	120.00	118.87	[C]
Inter. Pressure	12.25	12.25	12.25	12.25	12.25	[bar]
LP	5.00	5.00	5.00	5.00	5.00	[bar]
Sink mass flow	1.00	1.11	1.25	1.43	1.67	[Kg/s]
Injection mass flow	0.025	0.025	0.025	0.025	0.025	[Kg/s]
ABS inlet temp.	135.28	135.80	136.70	137.63	138.10	[C]
ABS outlet temp.	87.23	89.69	91.52	93.74	95.97	[C]
X_lean	0.36	0.36	0.36	0.36	0.35	[-]
X_rich	0.66	0.69	0.71	0.73	0.73	[-]
m_rich	0.26	0.29	0.31	0.34	0.35	[-]
m_lean	0.13	0.18	0.20	0.23	0.24	[-]
CR	0.50	0.64	0.66	0.69	0.70	[-]
ABS Heat Load	210.52	210.55	210.50	210.11	203.60	[KW]
DSB Cooling Load	151.54	148.22	145.02	141.68	137.51	[KW]
Pumpwork	0.97	0.95	0.92	0.90	0.88	[KW]
ShaftWork Comp-1	26.66	25.84	24.51	22.43	18.22	[KW]
Shaftwork Comp-2	31.34	36.55	41.72	47.31	49.88	[KW]
Total work	59.35	63.34	67.15	70.64	68.98	[KW]
COP	3.55	3.32	3.14	2.99	2.96	[-]
T_lift	50.00	44.99	39.93	34.85	28.94	[K]
COP_Lorentz	2.36	2.61	2.89	3.22	3.67	[-]
eta_lorentz	1.51	1.28	1.09	0.93	0.81	[-]

Table 7.7: ACHP model: Steady state results for different cycle configurations

7.3.2 Validation of ACHP model

During the experimental investigation, several boundary conditions were tested, including 60/60 °C, 65/65 °C, and 70/70 °C for sink-source inlet with injection at bearings, and with or without injection at the male-female rotor cavity. To validate the developed ACHP model in Dymola, experimental data was compared with a 60/60 °C setup, a sink mass flow rate of 0.478 kg/s, and a source mass flow rate of 0.518 kg/s. The results from both simulation and experimental investigation are explained here, followed by a deviation analysis (see Table D.2 in Appendix D) using normalized root mean square deviation (NRMSD) as discussed in section 6.5. The results presented are snippet form steady state data from simulation model and 500 series of data plot from the experimental data.

Figure 7.16: Performance validation of (a) heat load (b) cooling load (c) COP

Figure 7.16(a) shows a plot of heating duty versus time series data or steady-state data for the three 60 °C heat sink and heat source inlet temperatures. Experimentally, the heat load varies between 0 kW and 55 kW, while it reaches 60 kW in simulation. The simulation shows very steady-state behavior, while the experiment shows some fluctuation. The average deviation and NRMSD were recorded at 79% and 356%, respectively. Figure 7.16(b) shows the cooling load varies from 10 to 25 kW experimentally, while it is 45 kW theoretically in simulation, showing very steady-state conditions. The average deviation and NRMSD were recorded at 70% and 228%, respectively. Figure 7.16 (c) illustrates the COP increases with time series data or the average value of the steady state, while the simulation shows a COP of 4.9, almost constant, with an average deviation of 11% and 356%, respectively. The heating capacity of the system

follows a trend similar to that exhibited by the COP, as the heating COP is dependent on the heating duty.

Figure 7.17: Performance validation of (a) lean solution mass flow (b) compressor discharge temperature (c) heat source outlet

Figure 7.17(a) shows the trend of lean solution mass flow rate over a steady-state time interval. The experimental values fluctuate slightly due to cavitation of the circulation pump, while the simulation values show steady behavior. The values were recorded between 0 kg/s and 0.08 kg/s. The average deviation and NRMSD were recorded at 64% and 176%, respectively. Figure 7.17 shows the compressor discharge temperature versus steady-state value. The trend shows almost similar values, with an average deviation and NRMSD recorded at 15% and 21%, respectively, which are close to each other. Figure 7.17 shows the heat source outlet temperature between 40 °C and 70 °C, both theoretical and experimental. The experimental value shows higher compared to the theoretical, with a maximum deviation and NRMSD recorded at -66% and 40%, respectively.

Figure 7.18(a) shows the low-pressure value or desorber values between 4 and 8 bar in a steady state. The experimental values slightly change with the time series, while theoretically, they show very linear values. The maximum deviation and NRMSD were recorded at 3% and 18%, respectively, which are close to each other. Figure 7.18(b) represents the absorber or high pressure during the time intervals. The maximum value for experimental varies between 9 and 15 bar, while theoretically, it shows 17 bar, with deviation and NRMSD recorded at 41% and 73%, respectively. Figure 7.18(c) shows the mass flow rate of strong solution versus steady-state

Figure 7.18: Performance validation of (a) Low pressure/desorber (b) high pressure/absorber (c) strong solution mass flow rate

Figure 7.19: Performance validation of (a) heat sink outlet (b) shaft power (c) solution pump power

data. The values vary between 0 kg/s and 0.2 kg/s, with slight fluctuations showing density variation. The deviation between experimental and theoretical was 85% and 561%, respectively.

Figure 7.19(a) shows the heat sink outlet temperature varies between 50 °C and 75 °C during actual test conditions and 98 °C for the theoretical simulation. The deviation between the two values was recorded at 23% and 32%, respectively. The values bring good validation. Figure 7.19(b) shows the compressor shaft power, which increases over the time interval from 10 kW to 20 kW, while the simulation results show a constant 15 kW, with an average deviation of 27% and 41%, respectively. Figure 7.19(c) shows the values for the circulation pump, which pumps lean solution through the IHX. The values are less than 0 kW to 0.49 kW experimentally and 0.5 kW theoretically. The values are close enough, with an average deviation of 13% and 21%, respectively.

7.4 Simulation: Steam generation

In the model to analyze the performance of steam generation by a flash tank mechanism, the inlet boundary condition of the submodel was set to 4 bar and 120 °C for the hot water inlet. This pressurized hot water was flashed to a pressure of 1 bar, reaching the boiling point of water. The mass flow rate of the pressurized hot water was 1 kg/s, and it was assumed that the system could flash 25% and 50% of the pressurized hot water to steam. The system could flash 25% and 50% of the pressurized hot water to steam.

Figure 7.20: Ph diagram of steam generation path

The graph in Figure 7.20, plotted in DAVE illustrates the process on a pressure-enthalpy (P-h) diagram, showcasing three distinct phases of the flash tank mechanism:

- Phase 1: Pressurized Water The process begins with pressurized water at 120 °C and 4 bar. This is represented by the point on the left side of the graph where the specific enthalpy is relatively low.
- Phase 2: Low Pressure Steam The pressurized water is then flashed to a lower pressure of 1 bar, which results in reaching the boiling point and producing steam. This phase is depicted by the horizontal transition on the graph where the specific enthalpy increases significantly, representing the latent heat of vaporization.
- Phase 3: Pressurized Steam The steam generated in Phase 2, with a mass flow rate of either 0.25 kg/s or 0.5 kg/s, is then compressed to a higher pressure of 2 bar. The compression process also increases the temperature to 193 °C. This phase is shown by the vertical transition on the right side of the graph, where both pressure and specific enthalpy are higher compared to the

initial states.

Parameter	Value 1	Value 2	Value 3	Unit
Hot water inlet	120.00	120.00	120.00	[C]
Inlet Pressure	4.00	4.00	4.00	[bar]
Pressure Flash tank	2.00	2.00	2.00	[bar]
Mass flow	0.13	0.25	0.50	[Kg/s]
Enthalpy (Hot water)	503.95	503.95	503.95	[KJ/kg]
Comp. Shaftpower	23.27	45.76	92.03	[KW]
Steam temp	193.41	193.39	193.39	[C]
Heat Demand (steam)	300.12	716.57	1176.74	[KW]
Enthalpy (Steam)	2857.46	2857.42	2857.42	[KJ/Kg]
T_lift	73.41	73.39	73.39	[C]

Table 7.8: Steady state results of steam generation model

The performance of the steam generation by a flash tank mechanism is further quantified in Table 7.8. The mass flow rates examined are 0.13 kg/s, 0.25 kg/s, and 0.50 kg/s, and corresponding compressor shaft power needed for these steam mass flow rates are 23.27 kW, 45.76 kW, and 92.03 kW. Though the system performance for a super-heated steam mass flow of 0.13 kg/s is not discussed in this report.

7.5 Cascade configurations

To decide which cascade model has more advantage over others in terms of overall performance, a cascaded configuration of all simulated models discussed in earlier sections aimed at steam generation from pressurized hot water was further developed. The cascade configurations are constructed either with the R717-ACHP cycle or the R744-ACHP cycle, and the steam mass flow is either 0.25 kg/s or 0.5 kg/s. CO₂-F110 and CO₂-G110 denote a gas cooler pressure of 110 bar at the bottom cycle with a supply outlet of 70°C. For all configurations, sink and source inlet temperatures are identical. The configurations are presented in Table 7.9.

Figure 7.21 illustrate the comparative performance of different configurations for .25 kg/s of steam mas flow. The configurations analyzed include both R717-ACHP and R744-ACHP cycles, denoted with varying system identifiers.

Figure 7.21: Cascade configuration comparative performance for 0.25 kg/s steam mass flow

The shaft work required varies significantly among configurations. Here the shaft work includes work done in bottom cycle, top cycle and the axial compressor at flash tank outlet. NH₃-A1 requires the least shaft work at 269.42 kW, while CO₂-E1 and NH₃-E1 require the most at approximately 345.80 kW. This indicates that NH₃-A1 is the most efficient in terms of power consumption for the given steam mass flow. The steam output ranges from 620.03 kW to 641.01 kW. Configurations such as NH₃-A1, CO₂-A1, and CO₂-F110 produce the highest steam output of 641.01 kW. This is because the supply water enthalpy at the ACHP sink inlet is lowest at 293.37 KJ/kg for a temperature of 70°C, which is higher for higher supply temperatures. Hence, the difference between the steam outlet and sink inlet water enthalpy increases with the increase

Configuration	Cascade	Source / Sink inlet [C]	[Sink out] [C]	m_steam [Kg/s]
NH3-A1	ACHP-NH3	70	120	0.25
NH3-A2	ACHP-NH3	70	120	0.5
NH3-B1	ACHP-NH3	75	120	0.25
NH3-B2	ACHP-NH3	75	120	0.5
NH3-C1	ACHP-NH3	80	120	0.25
NH3-C2	ACHP-NH3	80	120	0.5
NH3-D1	ACHP-NH3	85	120	0.25
NH3-D2	ACHP-NH3	85	120	0.5
NH3-E1	ACHP-NH3	90	120	0.25
NH3-E2	ACHP-NH3	90	120	0.5
C02-A1	ACHP-CO2	70	120	0.25
C02-A2	ACHP-CO2	70	120	0.5
C02-B1	ACHP-CO2	75	120	0.25
C02-B2	ACHP-CO2	75	120	0.5
C02-C1	ACHP-CO2	80	120	0.25
C02-C2	ACHP-CO2	80	120	0.5
C02-D1	ACHP-CO2	85	120	0.25
C02-D2	ACHP-CO2	85	120	0.5
C02-E1	ACHP-CO2	90	120	0.25
C02-E2	ACHP-CO2	90	120	0.5
C02-F110	ACHP-CO2	70	120	0.25
C02-G110	ACHP-CO2	70	120	0.5

Table 7.9: System Configuration for economic evaluation

in sink inlet temperature.

The COP values also vary, with NH₃-A1 achieving the highest COP of 2.38, indicating the highest efficiency. In contrast, configurations like CO₂-E1 and NH₃-E1 have lower COP values around 1.79, showing less efficiency. The sink inlet temperature plays a crucial role in system performance. Lower sink inlet temperatures (e.g., 70°C) correlate with higher COP values and lower shaft work, as seen in configurations like NH₃-A1, CO₂-A1, and CO₂-F110.

Figure 7.22 illustrates the comparative performance of different cascade configurations for a 0.5

Figure 7.22: Cascade configuration comparative performance for 0.5 kg/s steam mass flow

kg/s steam mass flow. The configurations analyzed include both R717-ACHP and R744-ACHP cycles, denoted with varying system identifiers.

The shaft work required for each configuration shows considerable variation. NH₃-A2 requires the least shaft work at 315.70 kW, while CO₂-E2 and NH₃-E2 require the most at approximately 392.07 kW. This indicates that NH₃-A2 is the most efficient in terms of power consumption for the 0.5 kg/s steam mass flow.

The steam output ranges from 1240.07 kW to 1282.03 kW. Configurations such as NH₃-A2, CO₂-A2, and CO₂-G110 produce the highest steam output of 1282.03 kW. This is because the supply water enthalpy at the ACHP sink inlet is lowest at 293.37 KJ/kg for a temperature of 70°C, which is higher for higher supply temperatures. Hence, the difference between the steam outlet and sink inlet water enthalpy increases with the increase in sink inlet temperature. The COP values vary significantly, with NH₃-A2 achieving the highest COP of 4.06, indicating the highest efficiency. In contrast, configurations like CO₂-E2 and NH₃-E2 have lower COP values around 3.16, showing less efficiency.

The sink inlet temperature has a substantial impact on system performance. Lower sink inlet temperatures (e.g., 70°C) correlate with higher COP values and lower shaft work, as seen in configurations like NH₃-A2, CO₂-A2, and CO₂-G110.

7.6 Economic Analysis

The cascade configurations presented in Section 7.5 were evaluated based on the theory presented in Section 6.6. Detailed results of the economic analysis for each cascade configuration and the alternative gas burner have been presented in Appendix E. For the economic analysis, the interest rate was assumed to be 7% with an inflation rate of 3%, and the cascaded system is expected to operate 3500 hours per year. The gas burner investment cost and maintenance cost are assumed to be zero since it is considered already in place for process thermal energy demand. For each configuration producing 0.25 kg/s steam and 0.5 kg/s steam, the operating hours were constant and the present value of the alternative gas burner was calculated as the configuration heat output if the same heat load was generated by the gas burner. In this study, the electricity price was taken from Strøm.no [74] and the natural gas unit price was taken from Eurostat [30], as shown in Table 7.10.

Parameter	Symbol	Value
Interest rate [%]	i	7%
Inflation rate [%]	i _L	3%
Technical lifetime [years]	LT	15
Operating time [Hours/year]	H	3500
Gas burner efficiency	η_{NG}	0.9
Gas burner investment cost [Euro]	TCL _{NG}	0
Gas burner maintenance cost [Euro]	OMC _{NG}	0
Electricity Price [Euro/KWh]	El	0.037
Gas Price [Euro/KWh]	NG	0.05

Table 7.10: Fixed parameters applied in the economic analysis

Detailed results of the total capital investment and purchase equipment cost are also presented in Appendix E. The sizing of heat exchanger areas was determined based on the convective heat transfer coefficient presented in Section 6.1 and Equation 6.1. The conductive heat transfer coefficient value was based on a stainless steel heat exchanger, which was used in the calculation of the overall heat transfer coefficient for each HEX.

The cascade configurations were evaluated based on their economic performance, assuming an interest rate of 7% and an inflation rate of 3%, with systems expected to operate 3500 hours per year. The results demonstrate significant differences in the Net Present Value (NPV) and Payback Period (PB) among the configurations, highlighting the varying economic viability of each system. The NH₃-A2 configuration emerged as the most economically advantageous,

boasting the highest NPV of €1,557,429 and the shortest PB of 3.16 years as can be seen in figure 7.23. This system's steam demand is 1282.026 kW, and 0.5 kg/s of steam mass flow.

Figure 7.23: Effect of Total Capital Investment (TCI) change on Net Present Value (NPV) for cascade configurations.

Similarly, the CO₂-G110 configuration performed well, with an NPV of €1,510,450 and a PB of 3.25 years, also demonstrating steam mass flow of 0.5 kg/s. In contrast, the CO₂-E1 configuration was the least favorable economically. It showed a significantly lower NPV of €137,650 and a much longer PB of 8.97 years. The steam demand for this configuration is 641.013 kW and designed to generate 0.25 kg/s of steam.

7.6.1 Sensitivity analysis

Change in Capital investment

-Influence on Net Present value:

For the NH₃ configurations, the NH₃-A2 system shows the highest NPV, starting at €1,600,000 at 0% TCI. As TCI increases to 15%, the NPV decreases to €1,490,000, representing a reduction of approximately 6.9%. This configuration maintains a relatively high NPV despite the increase in TCI, indicating robust economic performance (see figure 7.23).

In the CO₂ configurations, the CO₂-G110 system exhibits the highest initial NPV of €1,560,000 at 0% TCI. With a 15% increase in TCI, the NPV decreases to €1,450,000, reflecting a reduction of about 7.1%. Similar to NH₃-A2, CO₂-G110 shows strong economic viability even with increased capital investment.

Figure 7.24: Effect of Total Capital Investment (TCI) change on Payback Period (PB) for cascade configurations.

-Influence on Payback Period:

The NH₃-A2 system also demonstrates favorable payback periods, starting at approximately 3.1 years at 0% TCI and increasing to 3.6 years with a 15% increase in TCI. This rise of around 16.1% suggests that while the payback period extends, it remains economically feasible (see figure 7.24).

For the CO₂ configurations, the CO₂-G110 system shows a payback period increase from about 3.2 years at 0% TCI to 3.7 years at 15% TCI, an increase of approximately 15.6%. This slight extension in the payback period indicates that the system remains economically attractive despite higher initial investments.

Change in Capital investment

- Net Present Value:

For the NH₃ configurations, the NH₃-A2 system shows a significant sensitivity to changes in electricity unit prices. The NPV for NH₃-A2 decreases from €1,600,000 at 0% change to €1,530,000 at a 15% increase in electricity prices, representing a reduction of approximately 4.4%. This relatively modest decline indicates that the NH₃-A2 configuration remains economically robust even with rising electricity costs (see figure 7.25).

In the CO₂ configurations, the CO₂-G110 system also demonstrates notable sensitivity. The NPV for CO₂-G110 decreases from €1,560,000 at 0% change to €1,490,000 at a 15% increase in

Figure 7.25: Effect of Unit Electricity Price change on Net Present value for cascade configurations

electricity prices, reflecting a reduction of about 4.5%. Similar to the NH₃-A2 system, CO₂-G110 maintains a high NPV despite increased electricity costs, showcasing its economic resilience.

Figure 7.26: Effect of Unit Electricity Price change on Payback Period (PB) for cascade configurations

- Payback Period

The payback period analysis indicates that the NH₃-A2 system's payback period increases slightly with higher electricity prices. Starting at approximately 3.1 years at 0% change, the payback period extends to around 3.2 years with a 15% increase in electricity prices, an increase of about 3.2%. This slight extension suggests that the system remains economically viable even

with higher operational costs (see figure 7.26).

For the CO₂ configurations, the CO₂-G110 system shows a similar trend. The payback period increases from about 3.2 years at 0% change to approximately 3.3 years at a 15% increase in electricity prices, representing an increase of about 3.4%. This minimal rise in the payback period indicates that the CO₂-G110 system continues to be a feasible option under higher electricity costs.

8 Discussion

The discussion section provides a summarized representation of the results and interpretation of the findings. Subsequently, the theoretical correlation of these results is discussed, highlighting the insights gained from the modeling, experimental and simulation efforts.

8.1 Discussion on R717 Simulation

The study focused on a two-stage ammonia heat pump, modeled in Dymola, a dynamic simulation environment in Modelica. Five configurations (A1 to A5) were evaluated, with supply temperatures ranging from 70°C to 90°C and corresponding condenser pressures from 33.89 bar to 52 bar. Each configuration's pressure-enthalpy behavior was analyzed using Log P-H diagrams, highlighting significant enthalpy changes at the evaporator and condenser stages, indicating effective heat absorption and rejection. The system was designed to supply a heat load of 610 kW with a varying load profile over a 24-hour period, sampled and simulated for 3600 seconds.

Increasing the supply temperature and condenser pressure resulted in higher pressures and enthalpies, consistent with the increased thermal demand. Consequently, the Coefficient of Performance (COP) decreased with higher temperatures and pressures due to the increased work required by the compressors. Configuration A1 demonstrated the highest COP of 3.50 at a supply temperature of 70°C and a condenser pressure of 33.89 bar, indicating it is the most efficient setup for the given conditions.

During the simulation, challenges such as varying the mass flow rate of cold city water at the condenser inlet to meet varying heat demands were encountered. For a 70°C supply temperature, Model A1 showed that the condenser outlet temperature approached the supply temperature during a 30 kW heat demand period (see Figure 8.1). Incorporating a thermal energy storage system could address this issue, ensuring the smooth operation of the bottom R717 cycle in the cascade high-temperature heat pump (HTHP) system. Thermal energy storage can enhance industrial processes by decreasing thermal energy consumption, providing a more stable and efficient operation for systems like the HTHP [49].

The desuperheat heat load was regulated by controlling the mass flow of cold city water, ensuring the superheated NH₃ at the desuperheater outlet was in the saturated vapor phase. The heat recovered from the desuperheater generated hot water outlet temperature of 120°C, necessitating the use of pressurized water to prevent the hot water from turning into steam. This recovered

Figure 8.1: Variation in system performance during variable heat load in R717 (a) change in condenser temperature (b) change in Shaft work, heat load

energy was designed to be sent to a thermal storage tank, as shown in Figure 5.5.

The simulation results showed that configurations A1 to A5 achieved steady-state performance after 200 seconds, meeting the target supply temperature at the condenser outlet. Configuration A1's heat load exceeded 610 kW, likely due to higher compressor mass flow from the high-pressure stage compared to other configurations.

In steady-state, the evaporator working pressure remained nearly constant due to the consistent cooling load, while intermediate and condenser pressures varied. The heat pump compressor's discharge temperature increased with higher condenser pressures. The desuperheater heat recovery peaked at 149.77 kW at a supply temperature of 85°C and a condenser pressure of 47.06 bar, the highest among all models.

The simulations were limited to steady-state conditions and did not account for potential variations in real-world applications. Real-world testing and validation of the simulation results are necessary to confirm the practical viability of the proposed configurations.

8.2 Discussion on R744 Simulation

A one-stage R744 heat pump was simulated as an alternative to R717 for the bottom cycle to produce steam for the HTHP cascade. The R744 cycle operates as a one-stage transcritical cycle designed with a piston compressor and an internal heat exchanger. This study modeled R744 heat pump cycles in Dymola to identify the best performance among five configurations (B1 to B5) with supply temperatures ranging from 70°C to 90°C and corresponding gas cooler pressures from 90 bar to 110 bar. The pressure-enthalpy behavior of each configuration was analyzed using Log P-H diagrams, illustrating phase changes and pressure variations within the system.

The heat rejection from the gas cooler was highest at 624 kW for configuration B1 and constant at 609 kW for all other configurations. The shaft power varied slightly across configurations, with configuration B1 requiring the most power at 231.58 kW and configuration B5 requiring the least power at 222.45 kW. The Coefficient of Performance (COP) decreased marginally from 2.81 in B1 to 2.63 in B5, a decrease of approximately 6.4%. The refrigerant mass flow decreased significantly from 3.57 kg/s in B1 to 3.03 kg/s in B5, indicating that less refrigerant is required as the pressure increases across configurations for a fixed gas cooler heat load.

Figure 8.2: Log P-h diagram for R744 model for predefined set configurations

Increasing the gas cooler pressure for higher supply temperature showed from the Log P-H diagram of cycle configurations B1-B5 that the throttle loss increases as the cooling load in the evaporator decreases with the increase of gas cooler pressure (Figure 8.2). This trend aligns with the study conducted by Wang et al. [85]. The COP remained at 2.81 for configurations B1 and B2 but began to drop as the gas cooler outlet temperature increased further, falling to 2.63 in configuration B5, as detailed in Table 7.4.

Figure 8.3: Gas cooler pressure impact on (a) Shaft Power (b) Refrigerant mass flow

To enhance the performance of the system, one approach is to increase the discharge pressure or discharge temperature [85]. To determine the optimum gas cooler pressure at 70°C, additional configurations (B1-90 to B1-120) were developed. The results indicated that shaft power decreases as the gas cooler pressure increases from 90 bar to 120 bar (Figure 8.3 (a)). Specifically, it dropped from 231.58 kW at 90 bar to 180.48 kW at 120 bar, an 18.9% reduction, indicating that higher gas cooler pressures result in lower energy consumption by the system. This is contrary to the findings by Illán-Gómez et al. [36], who observed that as the gas cooler pressure increases, the compressor’s power input (shaft work) also increases due to the higher specific compression work required. Conversely, the refrigerant mass flow decreases for higher gas cooler pressures due to the increase in refrigerant density, reducing volumetric flow rate (Figure 8.3 (b)).

The results indicate that while increasing gas cooler pressure can reduce the refrigerant mass flow and associated costs, it also leads to higher throttle losses and decreased COP. Overall, configuration B1-110, with a gas cooler pressure of 110 bar and a supply temperature of 70°C, exhibited the highest COP and the best overall performance, making it the most efficient choice among the configurations tested.

The simulations were limited to steady-state conditions and did not account for potential variations in real-world applications. Real-world testing and validation of the simulation results are necessary to confirm the practical viability of the proposed configurations.

8.3 Discussion on ACHP Experimental and Simulation Results

The ACHP system was modeled as the top cycle of the cascaded heat pump, using different sink and source inlet temperatures to investigate its performance in producing pressurized hot water and superheated steam. The ACHP cycle configurations, ranging from sink/source inlet temperatures of 70/70°C to 90/90°C, were evaluated in Dymola, focusing on key performance indicators such as the influence of lean solution mass flow rate on shaft power and circulation ratio, and the influence of rich ammonia solution mass flow rate on COP and circulation ratio. Five model configurations, C1, C2, C3, C4, and C5, were studied under various sink and source inlet temperatures ranging from 70°C to 90°C for fixed heat load and fixed sink and source mass flow rates in steady-state conditions.

In Table 7.7, it is shown that the pump work decreases from 0.97 kW to 0.88 kW as the lean solution mass flow rate increases from 0.13 to 0.24. This trend suggests that higher lean solution mass flow rates lead to lower pump work, which is contrary to the findings of Nordtvedt [59]. Nordtvedt [59] indicated that an increase in lean solution mass flow rate typically results in higher pump work due to the additional energy required to circulate a larger mass flow. In the experimental investigation at the "Osenbrück 4.0 Heat Pump," as presented in section 7.3.2, figures 7.17(a) and 7.19(c), the pump work also increases with the increase in lean solution mass flow rate, as investigated by Nordtvedt [59]. This discrepancy indicates that the Dymola model needs further improvement in terms of mass flow initialization, weak and rich solution mass fraction specification, and boundary condition adjustments.

The circulation ratio and strong solution mass fraction have a correlation for optimum COP, which was further investigated in this study. As the strong solution mass fraction increases, the COP decreases, and the circulation ratio increases with the increase of strong solution mass flow. Jensen [38] studied that as soon as the ammonia mass fraction is above a certain value, the circulation ratio has a specific value that maximizes the COP. This correlation can be further investigated by the developed model, but ensuring the boundary condition initialization values in the model for different components are varied accordingly.

The steady-state results from the Dymola simulation, summarized in Table 7.7, provided further insights into the system's performance under various configurations. The high pressure remained constant at 30 bar across all conditions, ensuring steady operation of the absorber. The low pressure was maintained at 5 bar, crucial for effective desorption in the desorber. The intermediate pressure of 12.25 bar was consistent across configurations, maintaining a heat load of 210 kW at the absorber. The sink mass flow rate varied from 1 kg/s to 1.667 kg/s, depending on the sink inlet temperature, to match the heat load.

Configuration C1, with a sink/source inlet temperature of 70/70°C, exhibited the highest COP and the lowest compressor shaft power, making it the most efficient configuration. As the source inlet temperature increased, the lean solution mass fraction decreased, reducing pump work and improving overall efficiency. Configuration C5, with a sink/source inlet temperature of 90/90°C, maintained a consistent heat load while adjusting the sink outlet temperature to optimize performance.

The validation of the ACHP model against experimental data revealed some discrepancies. While the simulation showed steady-state behavior, the experimental results exhibited fluctuations, particularly in heating and cooling loads. This is because the experimental values were picked for an assumed steady-state condition from a four-hour experiment, during which the control parameters were changed frequently to find the steady state. Also, the initialization in the mimic model of experimental investigation did not consider exact lean and rich solution mass fractions. In the experiment, it is also challenging to determine the exact value of strong and lean solution mass fractions due to the dynamic change in the density of the strong solution before expansion. The significant average deviation and NRMSD indicate potential areas for model refinement. Despite these variations, the trends in COP, compressor discharge temperature, and heat source outlet temperature were generally consistent between simulation and experimental results.

8.4 Discussion on Steam Generation and Cascade Configuration

The steam generation model presented in this study investigates a mass flow rate of 0.25 kg/s and 0.5 kg/s of superheated steam at 2 bar and 193°C. The model was not validated against real-world applications due to the unavailability of data. Eleven cascade configurations were further studied, combining CO₂-ACHP and NH₃-ACHP, consisting of all configurations studied in the R717, R744, and ACHP result sections as A1-A5, B1-B5, C1-C5. These configurations were combined to form the HTHP cascade for steam generation at a steam heat load of approximately 640 kW and 1282 kW for steam mass flows of 0.25 kg/s and 0.5 kg/s, respectively. The configurations are presented in Table 7.9.

Cascade configurations NH₃-A1 and CO₂-F110 showed the most effective system performance. NH₃-A1, with a COP of 2.379, consists of an R717 bottom cycle with a 70°C supply temperature and an ACHP top cycle with 70/70°C sink/source inlet temperatures, achieving a steam heat load of 641 kW and a 0.25 kg/s steam mass flow rate. CO₂-F110, with a COP of 2.173, is a cascaded HTHP combining an R744 bottom cycle with a 110 bar gas cooler pressure, a 70°C supply temperature, and an ACHP top cycle with 70/70°C sink/source inlet temperatures, also achieving a steam heat load of 641 kW and a 0.25 kg/s steam mass flow rate.

For a steam mass flow rate of 0.5 kg/s, configurations NH₃-A2 and CO₂-G110 showed the most effective system performance. NH₃-A2, with a COP of 4.061, consists of an R717 bottom cycle with a 70°C supply temperature and an ACHP top cycle with 70/70°C sink/source inlet temperatures. CO₂-G110, with a COP of 3.757, consists of an R744 bottom cycle with a 110 bar gas cooler pressure, a 70°C supply temperature, and an ACHP top cycle with 70/70°C sink/source inlet temperatures.

8.5 Discussion on Economic and Sensitivity Analysis

The economic evaluation of the cascade configurations was conducted to determine the most cost-effective and efficient systems for steam generation from pressurized hot water.

It should be noted that the purchase equipment cost (PEC) for components of the top and bottom cycle configurations were taken from Ommen et al. [60]. For components without available PEC data, prices were assumed based on similar components. For example, there was no available data on the R717 high-pressure compressor, so the PEC of the R717 low-pressure compressor was used. Additionally, the sizing of the flash tank, axial compressor for

steam generation, and pressurized hot water pump TCI were assumed by multiplying 150 Euros by 15% of the heating capacity of each cascade unit, as mentioned by Bataille et al. [16]. Due to these assumptions, the TCI calculation may not be entirely accurate. Therefore, a sensitivity analysis of 5%, 10%, and 15% changes in TCI was conducted to understand its impact on NPV and PB. According to Ommen et al. [60], electricity price can significantly affect NPV uncertainty. Thus, the influence of electricity price increases by 5%, 10%, and 15% was also investigated.

The NH₃-A2 configuration emerged as the most economically advantageous, boasting the highest Net Present Value (NPV) of €1,557,429 and the shortest Payback Period (PB) of 3.16 years. This configuration is highly efficient for generating a steam mass flow of 0.5 kg/s. Similarly, the CO₂-G110 configuration performed well, with an NPV of €1,510,450 and a PB of 3.25 years for the same steam mass flow. In contrast, the CO₂-E1 configuration was the least favorable economically, with an NPV of €137,650 and a PB of 8.97 years, indicating lower economic efficiency for a steam mass flow of 0.25 kg/s. These results indicate that NH₃-A2 and CO₂-G110 are more suitable for applications requiring high economic returns and operational efficiency.

The sensitivity analysis examined the impact of changes in Total Capital Investment (TCI) and electricity prices on economic performance. Both NH₃-A2 and CO₂-G110 configurations maintained high NPVs and feasible PBs even with a 15% increase in TCI, indicating strong economic robustness. Similarly, both configurations remained economically viable with only a slight reduction in NPV and a minimal increase in PB with a 15% rise in electricity prices.

9 Conclusion

The primary objective of this thesis was to investigate the potential of high-temperature heat pump (HTHP) technology, specifically the hybrid ammonia-water absorption compression heat pump (ACHP) system in a cascaded configuration. This system combines two alternate bottom cycles: a two-stage intercooler type NH_3 heat pump and an internal heat exchanger facilitated CO_2 heat pump. The focus was on producing hot water and steam for the meat processing industry to enhance energy efficiency and reduce greenhouse gas emissions, aligning with the European Union's sustainability and decarbonization goals.

Throughout this study, extensive modeling and experimental work were conducted to evaluate the performance of the ACHP system. Various system configurations were explored, and the results demonstrated that the ACHP system could effectively utilize low-temperature waste heat to produce high-pressure hot water and steam. Specifically, waste seawater at 15°C from an ammonia refrigeration condenser was upgraded to superheated steam at 193°C and 2 bar by the cascaded HTHP configurations. The CO_2 -ACHP and NH_3 -ACHP cascaded cycles emerged as particularly effective, achieving significant temperature lifts and high coefficients of performance (COP). The economic analysis further highlighted the system's feasibility and potential for cost savings, reinforcing its viability as a replacement for traditional fossil fuel-based steam boilers.

Summary of Key Findings

1. Efficiency Improvements:

- The ACHP cascade HTHP system showed marked efficiency gains over conventional steam boilers in steam generation.
- The system's COP was found to be 4.06 for the NH_3 -ACHP configuration and 3.75 for the CO_2 -ACHP configuration, indicating substantial efficiency improvements for producing 0.5 kg/s of superheated steam at 2 bar and 193°C .

2. Optimal Operating Conditions:

- Increasing the gas cooler pressure improved the efficiency of the CO_2 cycle. The optimum gas cooler pressure for the CO_2 heat pump cycle was 110 bar for a 70°C supply temperature, a 10°C evaporation temperature, with a COP of 3.46 and compressor work of 180.48 kW for a heat load of 624 kW at the gas cooler.

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- A higher condensation pressure reduced the efficiency of the NH₃ cycle. The NH₃ bottom cycle showed better performance at a condenser pressure of 34 bar, a 10°C evaporation temperature, and a 70°C condensation temperature to supply a heat load of 624 kW to the top ACHP cycle.

3. Performance of the Top Cycle:

- The top cycle of the proposed HTHP cascade, ACHP, performed better for a sink and source inlet of 70°C and 70°C, with sink and source mass flow rates of 1 kg/s and 1.2 kg/s respectively, and a heat load of 210 kW for producing pressurized hot water from the absorber outlet at 120°C.

4. Cascade Configuration Performance:

- The cascade configuration of the CO₂-ACHP and NH₃-ACHP showed better COP when pressurized hot water was expanded to steam. The COP of the CO₂-ACHP cycle was 3.75 and 2.17 for steam mass flows of 0.5 kg/s and 0.25 kg/s, and steam heat loads of 1282 kW and 641 kW respectively.
- The COP of the NH₃-ACHP cycle was 4.06 and 2.37 for steam mass flows of 0.5 kg/s and 0.25 kg/s, and steam heat loads of 1282 kW and 641 kW respectively.

5. Economic Viability:

- The payback period for the CO₂-ACHP cycle was found to be 3.25 and 7.65 years for steam mass flow rates of 0.5 kg/s and 0.25 kg/s respectively, with a Net Present Value (NPV) of 1.51 million Euros and 258,000 Euros respectively, compared to generating steam solely by a gas-fueled boiler with the same mass flow rate.
- The payback period for the NH₃-ACHP cycle was found to be 3.16 and 7.21 years for steam mass flow rates of 0.5 kg/s and 0.25 kg/s respectively, with an NPV of 1.56 million Euros and 305,000 Euros respectively, compared to generating steam solely by a gas-fueled boiler with the same mass flow rate.

The study has demonstrated the technical and economic feasibility of using a cascaded HTHP system with hybrid ammonia-water absorption compression technology for steam and hot water production in the meat processing industry. The significant efficiency improvements, optimal operating conditions, and favorable economic analysis support the adoption of this technology, contributing to energy efficiency and sustainability goals.

10 Suggestions for Further Work

The scope of this project is large, with its focus on cascaded HTHP systems for steam generation, energy recovery, and hot water generation. Consequently, it has not been possible to thoroughly investigate all the influencing factors. The simulation model includes assumptions and approximations of uncertain magnitude, which may lead to deviations in performance from a real steam generation heat pump system. The bottom cycles were not validated against a real heat pump configuration, which may lead to further deviations. The experimental validation of the ACHP top cycle against the Dymola model showed a large deviation in all system parameters studied, necessitating more experiments and modification of the simulation model accordingly to reduce the deviation. The sink outlet temperature investigated in this study was limited to 120°C; raising this temperature to 140°C may be investigated further to observe any system performance changes. Also, the results of the economic analysis are greatly dependent on the assumed investment cost of the components. An actual capital investment cost may positively or negatively influence the findings of this study.

The thermal demand profile is based on assumptions for the cascaded system in light of the meat processing plant. An actual thermal demand profile, required steam and hot water mass flow rate, temperature, and pressure in various meat processes will further help to customize the cascaded configuration. The developed models are not connected together to avoid deviation; rather, the boundary condition output of the bottom cycle was used as a boundary condition input for the preceding top cycle. In a combined model, the system needs further controlling to make the models more responsive and effective.

It is also suggested to conduct more literature studies on flash tank-based steam generation systems, the operational challenges, component sizing, compressor efficiency used in mechanical vapor compression cycles for steam generation, and compatibility of materials to withstand superheated steam temperatures. In this thesis, heat losses to the ambient are only regarded in the compressor models, and pressure losses in the system are not considered. In order to investigate the performance of the system in detail, this should be investigated. The overall heat transfer coefficient for ACHP absorber and desorber also needs further calculation as this was skipped in this study and assumed from other literature.

Thermal energy storage will enhance the energy efficiency of the cascaded HTHP. A more detailed investigation on incorporating TES with the bottom cycles, and the viability of incorporating it in the top cycle to store pressurized hot water at 120°C or above, can improve the system efficiency and alleviate operational challenges.

Additionally, further work should explore hydrocarbon-based heat pumps as an alternative to the ACHP top cycle. While this study included a literature review on hydrocarbon-based systems, their potential as an alternative method for steam generation warrants detailed modeling and experimental investigation. This would provide a comprehensive understanding of their feasibility and effectiveness compared to the current ACHP configurations, contributing to a broader range of efficient and sustainable solutions for industrial applications.

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Appendix A

A.1 Single Phase Heat Transfer Coefficient

For single-phase heat transfer, the correlation by Martin [53] can be applied. This semi-empirical correlation is based on an analogy to friction and uses the Moody friction factor, calculated as follows:

$$\frac{1}{\xi} = \cos(\phi) \left(0.18 \tan(\phi) + 0.36 \sin(\phi) + \xi_0 \sqrt{\cos(\phi)} + \frac{1 - \cos(\phi)}{3.8 \xi_{1.0}} \right)$$

Here, ϕ is the corrugation inclination angle ($\phi = 90^\circ - \beta$). The terms ξ_0 and $\xi_{1.0}$ are the friction factors for straight longitudinal flow ($\phi = 0^\circ$) and wavy longitudinal flow ($\phi = 90^\circ$), respectively.

For laminar flow ($\frac{Re}{\phi} < 2000$), the friction factors are given by:

$$\xi_0 = \frac{64\phi}{Re}$$
$$\xi_{1.0} = \frac{597\phi}{Re} + 3.85$$

For turbulent flow ($\frac{Re}{\phi} > 2000$), the friction factors are:

$$\xi_0 = \left(1.8 \log_{10} \frac{Re}{\phi} - 1.5 \right)^{-2}$$
$$\xi_{1.0} = \frac{39}{\left(\frac{Re}{\phi} \right)^{0.289}}$$

The Reynolds number is calculated using the mass flux G and the hydraulic diameter D_h :

$$Re = \frac{G \cdot D_h}{\eta}$$

where $D_h = 2b$, with b being the plate depth.

The Nusselt number, relating to the heat transfer coefficient, is determined using:

$$Nu = \Phi \cdot 0.122 \cdot Pr^{1/3} \left(\frac{\eta}{\eta_w} \right)^{1/6} \left(\xi \left(\frac{Re}{\phi} \right)^2 \sin(2\phi) \right)^{0.374}$$

Here, η is the dynamic viscosity, η_w is the viscosity at the exchanger surface temperature, and Pr is the Prandtl number.

The cross-sectional area for mass flux is $A_{\text{cross}} = N_{\text{ch}} \cdot L_W \cdot b$, where $N_{\text{ch}} = N_{\text{plates}} - 1$ (number of channels) and L_W is the plate width.

The heat transfer coefficient (α) is then related to the Nusselt number by:

$$\alpha = \frac{Nu \cdot \lambda}{D_h}$$

where λ is the thermal conductivity of the fluid.

A.2 Condensation and Gas Cooler Heat Transfer Coefficient

The condensation and gas cooler heat transfer coefficient ($\alpha_{r;l}$) for refrigerant in a plate heat exchanger is calculated using the correlation proposed by Kuo et al. [46]:

$$\alpha_{r;l} = 0.2092 \frac{k_l}{D_h} \text{Re}_l^{0.78} \text{Pr}_l^{1/3} \left(\frac{\mu_{l,\text{ave}}}{\mu_{l,\text{wall}}} \right)^{0.14}$$

where:

- k_l is the thermal conductivity of the liquid refrigerant.
- D_h is the hydraulic diameter.
- Re_l is the Reynolds number for the liquid refrigerant.
- Pr_l is the Prandtl number for the liquid refrigerant.
- $\mu_{l,\text{ave}}$ is the dynamic viscosity of the liquid refrigerant at the average temperature.
- $\mu_{l,\text{wall}}$ is the dynamic viscosity of the liquid refrigerant at the wall temperature.

Auxiliary correlations and definitions used in the calculation include:

Condensate Mass Fraction (C_o):

$$C_o = \left(\frac{\rho_g}{\rho_l} \right) \left(\frac{1 - X_m}{X_m} \right)^{0.8}$$

where ρ_g and ρ_l are the densities of the gas and liquid refrigerant, respectively, and X_m is the mass quality.

Liquid Froude Number (Fr_l):

$$\text{Fr}_l = \frac{G^2}{\rho_l^2 g D_h}$$

where G is the mass flux and g is the acceleration due to gravity.

Boiling Number (Bo):

$$Bo = \frac{q}{G h_{fg}}$$

where q is the heat flux and h_{fg} is the latent heat of vaporization.

Prandtl Number (Pr_l):

$$Pr_l = \frac{\mu_l c_{p,l}}{k_l}$$

where μ_l is the dynamic viscosity and $c_{p,l}$ is the specific heat of the liquid refrigerant at constant pressure.

Equivalent Reynolds Number (Re_{eq}):

$$Re_{eq} = \frac{G_{eq} D_h}{\mu_l}$$

where G_{eq} is the equivalent mass flux:

$$G_{eq} = G \left((1 - X_m) + X_m \left(\frac{\rho_l}{\rho_g} \right) \right)^{1/2}$$

A.3 Evaporation Heat Transfer Coefficient

For two-phase heat transfer during evaporation in plate heat exchangers, the correlation proposed by Ayub [13] is applied:

$$\alpha_{tp} = C \left(\frac{k_l}{d_e} \right) \left(\frac{Re_l^2 h_{fg}}{L_p} \right)^{0.4124} \left(\frac{p}{p_{cr}} \right)^{0.12} \left(\frac{65}{\beta} \right)^{0.35}$$

where:

- α_{tp} is the two-phase heat transfer coefficient.
- C is a constant, with typical values being 0.1121 for flooded and thermo-syphon systems, and 0.0675 for direct expansion (DX) systems.
- k_l is the thermal conductivity of the liquid phase.
- d_e is the equivalent diameter of the channel.
- Re_l is the Reynolds number for the liquid phase.
- h_{fg} is the latent heat of vaporization.

- L_p is the effective plate length.
- p is the system pressure.
- p_{cr} is the critical pressure of the fluid.
- β is the chevron angle of the plate heat exchanger.

A.4 Desorption

Táboas et al. [77] studied the thermal behavior of a two-phase ammonia-water mixture in a plate heat exchanger during desorption. They developed a correlation to determine whether desorption is governed by nucleate boiling or convective flow boiling, based on the velocities of vapor and liquid in the mixture:

$$u_{SL} = \frac{G(1-q)}{\rho_l}$$

$$u_{SV} = \frac{G \cdot q}{\rho_v}$$

where q is the quality of the mixture, and ρ_l and ρ_v are the densities of the liquid and vapor, respectively.

To assess the dominant desorption mechanism:

$$u_{SV} < 111.88u_{SL} + 11.848 \text{ [m/s]}$$

If this inequality is satisfied, the heat transfer coefficient (α) is:

$$\alpha = 5 \cdot Bo^{0.15} \cdot \alpha_{lo}$$

where α_{lo} is the liquid-only heat transfer coefficient calculated using Martin's correlation, and Bo is the boiling number defined as:

$$Bo = \frac{q''}{G \cdot h_{lv}}$$

If the inequality is not satisfied, the heat transfer coefficient is determined by the maximum of the two values:

$$\alpha = \max(F \cdot \alpha_{lo}, 5 \cdot Bo^{0.15} \cdot \alpha_{lo})$$

The Chisholm two-phase enhancement factor (F) and the Lockhart-Martinelli factor (X_{tt}) are calculated as follows:

$$F = \left(1 + \frac{3}{X_{tt}} + \frac{1}{X_{tt}^2}\right)^{0.2}$$

$$X_{tt} = \left(\frac{\eta_l}{\eta_v}\right)^{0.1} \left(\frac{1-q}{q}\right)^{0.9} \left(\frac{\rho_v}{\rho_l}\right)^{0.5}$$

A.5 Absorption

For calculating the heat transfer coefficient of the ammonia-water mixture in the absorber, the Silver/Bell-Ghaly method is used [17]. This method derives the heat transfer coefficient from the vapor and condensate layer heat transfer coefficients, along with a correction factor (Z):

$$\alpha = \left(\frac{1}{\alpha_{lo}} + \frac{Z}{\alpha_{vo}}\right)^{-1}$$

The Nusselt number for the liquid-only flow (Nu_{lo}) is calculated using:

$$Nu_{lo} = 4.188 \cdot Re_{lo}^{0.4} \cdot Pr^{1/3}$$

Here, α_{vo} is the vapor-only heat transfer coefficient obtained from Martin's correlation, and α_{lo} is the condensate layer heat transfer coefficient corrected for two-phase flow effects.

The correction factor (Z) is calculated as:

$$Z = q \cdot c_{p,v} \cdot \frac{dT}{dh}$$

where q is the vapor mass fraction, $c_{p,v}$ is the specific heat of the vapor phase, and $\frac{dT}{dh}$ is the gradient of the equilibrium absorption curve.

Appendix B

B.1 Heat exchangers geometry

	Evaporator	Condenser	Desuperheater
Number of Plates	40	40	40
Length (m)	0.9	0.9	0.25
Width (m)	0.111	0.111	0.111
Corrugation/chevron angle β ($^\circ$)	50	65	65
Wall thickness t (m)	0.0004	0.0004	0.0004
Pattern amplitude (p) (m)	0.002	0.002	0.002
Pattern wave length/corrugation pitch: P_c (m)	0.007	0.007	0.007
D_p (m)	0.05	0.05	0.05
L_p (m)	0.416	0.416	0.416
Plate width L_w (m)	0.111	0.111	0.111
$A_p = L_p \times L_w$ (m ²)	0.05	0.05	0.05
Pressing Depth $b = p - t$ (m)	0.0016	0.0016	0.0016
Channel flow area $A_x = b \times L_w$ (m ²)	7.39E-05	7.38E-05	7.386E-05
$X = (\pi \times b)/P_c$	0.718	0.718	0.718
ϕ (Surface enlargement factor)	1.119	1.119	1.119
Effective area of heat transfer A_{eff} (m ²) $\{\phi \times A_p\}$	0.0516	0.0516	0.0516
D_h (Hydraulic Diameter) m (2b)	0.0032	0.0032	0.0032

Table B.1: Heat Exchangers Geometric Parameters for R717 Cycle

	Evaporator	Gascooler	IHX
Number of Plates	40	40	20
Length (m)	0.9	0.9	0.25
Width (m)	0.111	0.111	0.111
Corrugation/chevron angle β ($^\circ$)	50	65	65
Wall thickness t (m)	0.0004	0.0004	0.0004
Pattern amplitude (p) (m)	0.002	0.002	0.002
Pattern wave length/corrugation pitch: P_c (m)	0.007	0.007	0.007
D_p (m)	0.05	0.05	0.05
L_p (m)	0.416	0.416	0.416
Plate width L_w (m)	0.111	0.111	0.111
$A_p = L_p \times L_w$ (m ²)	0.05	0.05	0.05
Pressing Depth $b = p - t$ (m)	0.0016	0.0016	0.0016
Channel flow area $A_x = b \times L_w$ (m ²)	7.39E-05	7.38E-05	7.386E-05
$X = (\pi \times b)/P_c$	0.718	0.718	0.718
ϕ (Surface enlargement factor)	1.119	1.119	1.119
Effective area of heat transfer A_{eff} (m ²) $\{\phi \times A_p\}$	0.0516	0.0516	0.0516
D_h (Hydraulic Diameter) m (2b)	0.0032	0.0032	0.0032

Table B.2: Heat Exchangers Geometric Parameters for R744 Cycle

	Desorber	Absorber	IHX
Number of Plates	40	40	40
Length (m)	0.9	0.9	0.25
Width (m)	0.111	0.111	0.111
Corrugation/chevron angle β ($^\circ$)	50	65	65
Wall thickness t (m)	0.0004	0.0004	0.0004
Pattern amplitude (p) (m)	0.002	0.002	0.002
Pattern wave length/corrugation pitch: P_c (m)	0.007	0.007	0.007
D_p (m)	0.05	0.05	0.05
L_p (m)	0.416	0.416	0.416
Plate width L_w (m)	0.111	0.111	0.111
$A_p = L_p \times L_w$ (m ²)	0.05	0.05	0.05
Pressing Depth $b = p - t$ (m)	0.0016	0.0016	0.0016
Channel flow area $A_x = b \times L_w$ (m ²)	7.39E-05	7.38E-05	7.386E-05
$X = (\pi \times b)/P_c$	0.718	0.718	0.718
ϕ (Surface enlargement factor)	1.119	1.119	1.119
Effective area of heat transfer A_{eff} (m ²) $\{\phi \times A_p\}$	0.0516	0.0516	0.0516
D_h (Hydraulic Diameter) m (2b)	0.0032	0.0032	0.0032

Table B.3: Heat Exchangers Geometric Parameters for ACHP Cycle

Parameter	B1-90	B1-95	B1-100	B1-105	B1-110	B1-115	B1-120	Unit
Ref. mass flow	3.57	2.88	2.56	2.38	2.28	2.21	2.16	[Kg/s]
GC pressure	90.00	95.00	100.00	105.00	110.00	115.00	120.00	[bar]
Low Pressure	33.17	32.41	32.10	31.98	31.97	32.01	32.07	[bar]
Comp. discharge	96.26	104.51	109.62	113.63	117.38	121.10	124.79	[$^\circ$ C]
Heat Load	624.00	624.00	624.00	624.00	624.00	624.00	624.00	[KW]
Sink outlet	70.00	70.00	70.00	70.00	70.00	70.00	70.00	[$^\circ$ C]
Gas cooler outlet	39.03	35.92	30.82	26.29	23.03	20.84	19.35	[$^\circ$ C]
Subcooler outlet	37.49	32.04	25.94	21.38	18.36	16.42	15.13	[$^\circ$ C]
Cooling Load	412.50	435.01	443.51	446.17	445.92	444.19	441.76	[KW]
Sink mass flow	2.62	2.62	2.62	2.62	2.62	2.62	2.62	[Kg/s]
Shaft power	222.45	197.51	186.27	181.58	180.48	181.34	183.20	[KW]
COP	2.81	3.16	3.35	3.44	3.46	3.44	3.41	[-]

Table B.4: R744: steady state simulation result for optimum gas cooler pressure

B.2 Dymola initial values for models and their components

Component	Compressor	Compressor	Expansion	Injection
	LP	HP	Valve	
Controlling Component	rotary boundary	rotary boundary	OrificeValve	OrificeValve
Variable type	Speed	Speed	Effective flow area	Effective flow area
Condition	use_nInput: True	use_nInput: True	TRUE	TRUE
Controller type	PI	PI	PI	PI
Invert feedback	FALSE	FALSE	FALSE	FALSE
Integral parameter type	T_i	T_i	T_i	T_i
k	1	1	0.1×10^{-12}	1.00×10^{-10}
T_i	20 s	10 s	0.5 s	150 s
y_{\max}	100	100	1×10^{-4}	0.1
y_{\min}	0.1	0.1	1×10^{-18}	1.00×10^{-16}
y_{initial}	70	30	4.75×10^{-6}	5.30×10^{-7}
Setpoint Variable	Sinkoutlet Temp.	Interm. pressure	High pressure	Compressor Discharge
Setpoint value	120 °C	12.25 bar	30 bar	180 °C

Table B.5: Controller parameters and setpoints for ACHP model components.

System	R717		ACHP		R744
Compressor	LP	HP	LP	HP	One stage
Compressor type	effCompressor	effCompressor	effCompressor	effCompressor	effCompressor
Use mechanical port	TRUE	TRUE	TRUE	TRUE	TRUE
Displacement	2.17E-03	1.75E-03	1.29E-03	4.45E-04	2.05E-04
λ	0.8	0.8	0.8	0.8	0.8
η	0.7	0.7	0.7	0.7	0.7
Condition: Supply temp	120°C	120°C	70°C	70°C	70°C

Table B.6: Compressor parameters for R717, ACHP, and R744 systems.

Variable	Value
Compressor type	effCompressor
Use mechanical port	TRUE
Displacement [m ³] (70 °C supply temp.)	0.000205004
Volumetric efficiency	0.8
Isentropic efficiency	0.7

Table B.7: R744: Compressor Specifications for Dymola

Appendix C

C.1 Initial values for cycles calculated in Refprop

Component	Temperature [°C]	Pressure [bar]	Density [kg/m ³]	Enthalpy [kJ/kg]	Entropy [kJ/kg K]
Evaporator_inlet	10	6.166	624.79	392.17	1.6496
Evaporator_outlet	11	6.166	4.8794	1617.5	5.9757
LPComp_inlet	11	6.166	4.8794	1617.5	5.9757
LPComp_outlet_isoentropic	70.471	14.46	9.5079	1735.9	5.9757
LPComp_outlet	89.21	14.46	8.8385	1786.6	6.1196
Intercooler_inlet_comp	89.21	14.46	8.8385	1786.6	6.1196
Intercooler_outlet	37.414	14.46	583.76	523.4	2.0871
Intercooler_inlet_condenser	37.414	14.46	35.69	856.9	3.1609
HPComp_inlet	89.21	14.46	8.8385	1786.6	6.1196
HPComp_outlet_isoentropic	165.12	33.89	17.358	1939.2	6.1196
HPComp_outlet	188.79	33.89	16.179	2004.6	6.265
DSP_inlet	188.79	33.89	16.179	2004.6	6.265
DSP_outlet	70.997	33.89	27.073	1629.2	5.3155
Condenser_inlet	70.997	33.89	27.073	1629.2	5.3155
Condenser_outlet	27	33.89	602.2	473.69	1.9137
Source_inlet	13	4	999.52	54.986	0.19523
Source_outlet	10	4	999.85	42.41	0.15105
Sink_inlet	13	4	999.52	54.986	0.19523
Sink_outlet	90	4	965.45	377.29	1.1926

Table C.1: Configuration A1: Initial values from REFPROP used for Dymola model

Component	Temperature [°C]	Pressure [bar]	Density [kg/m ³]	Enthalpy [kJ/kg]	Entropy [kJ/kg K]
Evaporator_inlet	9.99	45.02	861.17	225.71	1.09
Evaporator_outlet	19.09	45.02	135.11	422.91	1.78
LP_tank_inlet	19.09	45.02	135.11	422.91	1.78
LP_tank_outlet	19.09	45.02	135.11	422.91	1.78
SC_IHEX_inlet	19.09	45.02	135.11	422.91	1.78
SC_IHEX_outlet	24.09	45.02	124.61	434.16	1.82
Comp_inlet	29.09	45.02	111.90	450.51	1.88
Comp_outlet_isonetropic	79.46	90.00	190.25	480.69	1.88
Comp_outlet	84.08	90.00	183.22	488.24	1.90
GC_inlet	84.08	90.00	183.22	488.24	1.90
GC_outlet	27.59	90.00	772.98	267.67	1.21
SubCooler_inlet_HP	27.59	85.00	759.38	270.00	1.22
SubCooler_outlet_HP	22.59	85.00	812.89	253.33	1.17
Source_inlet	13.00	4.00	999.52	54.99	0.20
Source_outlet	10.00	4.00	999.85	42.41	0.15
Sink_inlet	13.00	4.00	999.52	54.99	0.20
Sink_outlet	74.08	4.00	975.52	310.46	1.00

Table C.2: R744 model: Initial values from REFPROP to initialise in Dymola

Component	NH3 [mass frac- tion]	Mass flow [Kg/s]	Temperature [C]	Pressure [bar]	Density [Kg/m3]	Enthalpy [KJ/Kg]	Entropy [KJ/Kg- K]
Abs_in	0.65	0.253	413.15	3	32.269	1274.1	4.29
Abs_out	0.65	0.253	363.15	3	687.33	437.88	2.13
Dsb_in	0.65	0.253	297.15	0.6	109.41	130.07	1.21
Dsb_out	0.65	0.253	338.15	0.5	6.5189	950.41	3.83
comp_in	0.995	0.121	338.15	0.5	3.1329	1767	6.56
Pump_in	0.65	0.253	296.14	0.5	768.48	87.112	1.07
IHX_hot_stream_in	0.65	0.253	363.15	3	687.33	437.88	2.13
IHX_hot_stream_out	0.65	0.253	345.94	3	711.45	347.574	1.87
IHX_cold_stream_in	0.32	0.253	338.15	3	833.24	183.41	1.3
IHX_cold_stream_out	0.32	0.253	358.15	3	813.52	283.75	1.59
Comp1 Outlet_basic	0.995	0.121	412.79	1.22	6.3246	1924.9	6.56
Comp1_isoentropic	0.995	0.121	440.05	1.22	5.882	1992.571	6.72
Comp2_out	0.995	0.273	529.69	3	12.055	2197	6.72
Comp2_out_isoentropic	0.995	0.273	562.14	3	11.267	2284.612	6.88
Injection	0.9336	0.273	447.15	1.22	4.1254	2181	6.3
Point_mixing							
Source_inlet	0	1.2	343.15	0.4	977.9	293.37	0.95
Source_outlet	0	1.2	302.15	0.4	996.08	121.92	0.42
Sink_inlet	0	1	358.15	0.4	968.75	356.28	1.13
Sink_outlet	0	1	408.15	0.4	930.58	567.8	1.69

Table C.3: ACHP model: Initial values from REFPROP to initialise in Dymola

Appendix D

D.1 Test rig operation procedure

Before starting the test, the auxiliary system must be prepared and heated to maintain a stable temperature on both the sink and source sides. All system components are powered on, and the auxiliary system pump is activated. The temperatures in the buffer tank, heat source, and sink inlets are then set accordingly [4].

1. Initial Setup:

- The expansion valves in the heat pump system are fully opened.
- The solution pump is started to circulate the lean solution throughout the system, aiding in heating and injection.

2. Compressor Activation:

- The compressor is activated, and its speed is gradually increased to 30%, eventually reaching the target values.
- Simultaneously, the main injection valve is opened 10-15% to provide lubrication for the bearing and shaft seal.

3. Adjustments:

- The injection valve or mass flow rate is adjusted based on the performance of the compressor and test rig.
- Once the desorber pressure and heat source temperature stabilize, the expansion valve is gradually closed to generate high pressure for complete absorption on the absorber side.
- The speeds of the solution pump and compressor are adjusted to meet the desired capacity and operational parameters.
- Simultaneously, the liquid injection flow rates to various compressor ports are adjusted using flow setting valves.
- The mass flow rates in the heat source and sink circuits are set to the specified values.

4. Steady-State Operation:

- The system is operated until steady-state conditions are reached.
- Data is continuously logged via the Data Acquisition System (DAQ) throughout the experiment for thorough analysis and monitoring.

D.2 Components Specification

The test rigs key component specifications are summarized below:

Key Component	Type	Features
Compressor	Screw	Volumetric ratio: 3.65 Max speed: 3600 rpm Swept volume: 350 m ³ /h
Solution Pump	Centrifugal	Max flow rate: 0-4.5 m ³ /h Max pressure head: 200 m Pressure: 20 bar
Expansion valve	ICM 20-A	Max. Working Pressure: 52 bar Kv value: 0.600 m ³ /h
Pumps (Source & sink)	SILH-50-D-4H	Volume flow rate: 1.2 l/s Max delivery head: 30 m
Desorber	Nickel braze Plate heat exchanger (PHE)	Heat transfer area: 2.22 m ² Overall length: 0.53 m Overall width: 0.11 m
IHX	Nickel braze Plate heat exchanger (PHE)	Heat transfer area: 0.61 m ² Overall length: 0.31 m Overall width: 0.11 m
Absorber	Nickel braze Plate heat exchanger (PHE)	Heat transfer area: 2.22 m ² Overall length: 0.53 m Overall width: 0.11 m
High & Low pressure separators	SS316L 1.4404 EN10028-7:2016	LP+HP: 40 bar Temperature: -20 to 200°C Volume: 36/210 L

Table D.1: Design specification of the key components of the experimental test rig

Parameters	Experiment	Simulation	NRMSD	
	Value	Value	Deviation	
Low Pressure [bar]	5.73	5.88	3%	18%
High Pressure [bar]	10.10	17.24	41%	73%
Mass Flow Rich Solution [Kg/s]	0.03	0.19	85%	561%
Mass Flow Lean Solution [Kg/s]	0.05	0.13	64%	176%
Discharge Temperature [°C]	89.18	104.73	15%	21%
Source Outlet Temperature [°C]	68.72	41.49	-66%	40%
Sink Outlet Temperature [°C]	70.29	90.85	23%	32%
Shaft Power [KW]	11.08	15.08	27%	41%
Pump Power [KW]	0.39	0.45	13%	21%
Heating Load [KW]	15.90	74.47	79%	356%
Cooling Load [KW]	13.05	43.39	70%	228%
COP	1.37	4.80	71%	250%
T_lift [°C]	21.98	30.85	29%	49%

Table D.2: Root mean squared deviation of simulation and experimental data for ACHP

Appendix E

E.1 Economic analysis results

Cycle	Component	Xy	Unit	PEC (Euro)	TCI (Euro)
ACHP	Compressor	312.79	m3/h	17,258.39	71,794.89
	Compressor motor	61.25	KW	5,467.78	22,745.96
	Pump	1.02	KW	1,244.59	5,177.48
	Absorber	3.81	m2	4,107.09	17,085.51
	Desorber	10.12	m2	8,968.45	37,308.73
	Internal HEX	1.01	m2	1,423.70	5,922.60
	Receiver HP	0.04	m3	1,064.19	4,427.03
	Separator	0.21	m3	3,408.19	14,178.07
CO2	Compressor	36.90	m3/h	14,118.94	58,734.79
	Compressor motor	166.05	KW	8,208.82	34,148.69
	Evaporator	42.93	m2	28,496.16	118,544.01
	Gas cooler	10.92	m2	9,529.16	39,641.30
	Internal HEX	1.76	m2	2,216.99	9,222.68
	Separator	0.21	m3	13,690.63	56,953.00
NH3	Compressor 1	389.98	m3/h	19,962.88	83,045.60
	Compressor motor 1	91.21	KW	5,561.04	23,133.94
	Compressor 2	315.89	m3/h	17,371.09	72,263.72
	Compressor motor 2	81.31	KW	5,160.96	21,469.58
	Evaporator	19.15	m2	14,940.53	62,152.63
	Desuperheater	0.37	m2	640.50	2,664.50
	Condenser	6.69	m2	6,443.90	26,806.64
	Intercooler	0.21	m3	2,479.99	10,316.75
	Separator	0.21	m3	2,479.99	10,316.75
Steam	Compressor and utilities	0.25	kg/s	14,422.79	59,998.82
	Compressor and utilities	0.50	kg/s	28,845.59	119,997.63

Table E.1: Component Cost Analysis for Different Cycles in steam generation

System	Q (Steam) [KW]	COP	TCI [Euro]	OMC [Euro]	Fuel cost NG [Euro]	PV (HTHP) [Euro]	PV Gas burner [Euro]	NPV HTHP [Euro]	PBP [Euro]
NH3-2	1282.026	4.06	610,808.01	122,161.60	249,282.83	1,238,889.10	2,796,318.59	1,557,429.48	3.16
C02-G110	1282.026	3.76	615,882.39	123,176.48	249,282.83	1,285,868.43	2,796,318.59	1,510,450.15	3.25
NH3-4	1271.551	3.66	610,808.01	122,161.60	247,246.03	1,290,026.10	2,773,470.81	1,483,444.71	3.27
C02-A2	1282.026	3.49	615,882.39	123,176.48	249,282.83	1,327,197.64	2,796,318.59	1,469,120.95	3.31
NH3-6	1261.066	3.43	610,808.01	122,161.60	245,207.28	1,322,979.81	2,750,601.23	1,427,621.42	3.36
C02-B2	1271.551	3.42	615,882.39	123,176.48	247,246.03	1,335,560.74	2,773,470.81	1,437,910.07	3.36
C02-C2	1261.066	3.32	615,882.39	123,176.48	245,207.28	1,347,219.39	2,750,601.23	1,403,381.85	3.42
NH3-8	1250.571	3.30	610,808.01	122,161.60	243,166.58	1,340,496.81	2,727,709.84	1,387,213.03	3.43
C02-D2	1250.571	3.22	615,882.39	123,176.48	243,166.58	1,360,612.61	2,727,709.84	1,367,097.22	3.48
NH3-10	1240.066	3.16	610,808.01	122,161.60	241,123.94	1,360,903.17	2,704,796.63	1,343,893.46	3.51
C02-E2	1240.066	3.16	615,882.39	123,176.48	241,123.94	1,367,373.15	2,704,796.63	1,337,423.48	3.54
NH3-1	641.013	2.38	550,809.20	110,161.84	124,641.42	1,092,733.50	1,398,159.29	305,425.79	7.22
C02-F110	641.013	2.17	555,883.57	111,176.71	124,641.42	1,139,712.83	1,398,159.29	258,446.46	7.66
NH3-3	635.7755	2.11	550,809.20	110,161.84	123,623.01	1,143,870.50	1,386,735.41	242,864.91	7.78
C02-A1	641.013	2.00	555,883.57	111,176.71	124,641.42	1,181,042.04	1,398,159.29	217,117.26	8.07
NH3-5	630.533	1.96	550,809.20	110,161.84	122,603.64	1,176,824.21	1,375,300.62	198,476.41	8.25

Table E.2: Summary of economic analysis for different system configurations-A

System	Q (Steam) [KW]	COP	TCI [Euro]	OMC [Euro]	Fuel cost NG [Euro]	PV (HTHP) [Euro]	PV Gas burner [Euro]	NPV HTHP [Euro]	PBP [Euro]
C02-B1	635.7755	1.95	555,883.57	111,176.71	123,623.01	1,189,405.14	1,386,735.41	197,330.26	8.28
C02-C1	630.533	1.89	555,883.57	111,176.71	122,603.64	1,201,063.79	1,375,300.62	174,236.83	8.54
NH3-7	625.2855	1.88	550,809.20	110,161.84	121,583.29	1,194,341.21	1,363,854.92	169,513.71	8.58
C02-D1	625.2855	1.83	555,883.57	111,176.71	121,583.29	1,214,457.01	1,363,854.92	149,397.90	8.84
NH3-9	620.033	1.79	550,809.20	110,161.84	120,561.97	1,214,747.57	1,352,398.31	137,650.74	8.97
C02-E1	620.033	1.79	555,883.57	111,176.71	120,561.97	1,221,217.55	1,352,398.31	131,180.77	9.08
Gas Burner	641.013	0.90	-	-	124,641.42	-	1,398,159.29	-	-

Table E.3: Summary of economic analysis for different system configurations-B

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